

**The Impact of Saudi Arabia's Free Education System and Allowance
Programs on Access to Education, Equity, and Student Learning Outcomes**

by

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Abstract

This study explores the transformative influence of Saudi Arabia's education policy, with a special emphasis on the evolution of stipend allocation and its implications for academic advancement and personal well-being. This study illuminates the profound shifts in Saudi Arabia's educational landscape, propelled by a strategic realignment of financial assistance programs that incorporate distance learning and internet-based learning modalities. Drawing on Bandura's Social Cognitive Theory and Adams' Equity Theory, the study explains how these policies boost student motivation while creating a supportive learning environment advantageous to overall growth and development. The findings highlight Saudi Arabia's dedication to promoting educational diversity, accessibility, and empowerment, establishing the country as a global leader in educational excellence.

Keywords: Educational reform; Socioeconomic impact; Personal well-being; Policy effectiveness; Holistic development

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INTRODUCTION

Purpose of the Study

The goal of this study is to investigate the influence of Saudi Arabia's free education system and stipend programs on educational access, equity, and student outcomes, especially in light of the COVID-19 pandemic. Social justice theory, the capacity approach, and human capital theory are used to create a theoretical framework for this research.

Based on the ideas of philosophers such as John Rawls and Amartya Sen, social justice theory investigates the ideals of fairness, equal chances, and eliminating social inequities in education. A just society, according to Rawls (1971), should ensure that all persons have equal access to required resources, including education. Sen (2000) highlights the importance of education in enabling people to live fulfilling lives and attain their full potential. In this study, we will use social justice theory to investigate how Saudi Arabia's free education system and stipend programs help to improving educational access and lowering disparities, thereby advancing social justice in the education sector.

Sen's (1986) capacity approach focuses on persons' capacities and freedoms rather than just on their material well-being. It highlights the value of education in broadening individuals' potential, allowing them to follow their dreams and live fulfilled lives. The capability approach provides a lens through which to understand how Saudi Arabia's educational initiatives, such as free education and stipend programs, contribute to enhancing individuals' capabilities by providing them with the resources and opportunities to develop their knowledge, skills, and agency.

Gary Becker (2009) proposed human capital theory, which states that education is an investment in human capital, which fosters economic growth and development. Individuals gain knowledge, skills, and capacities through education, according to this notion, making them more

productive and valuable in the job market. Human capital theory can help us comprehend how Saudi Arabia's free education system and stipend programs can potentially improve students' academic experiences, retention rates, and future career possibilities. Saudi Arabia hopes to produce a professional and knowledgeable workforce that can contribute to the country's economic development and advancement by investing in education.

Using social justice theory, the capability approach, and human capital theory as conceptual frameworks, this study seeks to examine the influence of Saudi Arabia's free education system and stipend programs on educational access, equity, and student results. These ideas serve as a framework for understanding the fundamental principles, beliefs, and benefits of these educational programs. Furthermore, they help frame the research within broader theoretical views and contribute to the existing body of knowledge on education, social justice, and human development.

Context

The socio-cultural and economic impact of the COVID-19 pandemic has caused considerable changes in Saudi Arabia's school system. Because of the epidemic, traditional face-to-face training has given way to online and distant learning modalities. It is critical to investigate the socio-cultural elements and dynamics that influence educational practices in order to comprehend the context in which the school system operates during the epidemic. In this context, theoretical frameworks such as sociocultural theory and the community of inquiry model might provide useful insights.

Lev Vygotsky's sociocultural theory emphasizes the relevance of social interaction and cultural context in determining learning and cognitive development. According to this theory, learning is a social process that takes place within a specific cultural environment through

collaboration, dialogue, and shared experiences (Vygotsky, 1978). Sociocultural theory can help illuminate the obstacles and opportunities associated with contact, collaboration, and knowledge building in virtual settings in the context of remote learning in Saudi Arabia during the epidemic. It emphasizes the necessity of building supportive and socially engaging learning environments, even in online settings, in order to provide students with meaningful learning experiences.

Garrison *et al.* (1999) presented the community of inquiry model as a framework for analyzing and evaluating the quality of online learning experiences. Three interconnected elements are identified by the model: cognitive presence, social presence, and teaching presence. The ability of learners to generate and confirm meaning through sustained thinking and speech is referred to as cognitive presence. The degree of connectedness, social engagement, and community building among learners is referred to as social presence. Teaching presence entails educators designing, facilitating, and directing online learning events. Using the community of inquiry approach, this study may investigate the dynamics of distant learning in Saudi Arabia during the pandemic and assess how well cognitive presence, social presence, and instructional presence are established in online educational environments.

This study can acquire insights into the dynamics of remote learning and the socio-cultural elements impacting educational practices in Saudi Arabia during and post the COVID-19 epidemic by applying sociocultural theory and the community of inquiry paradigm. These theoretical frameworks serve as a lens for examining the challenges and opportunities related with online education, such as concerns of interaction, cooperation, and knowledge building. Furthermore, they provide guidelines for developing supportive and socially interactive virtual learning environments, as well as measuring the quality of online learning experiences. This study can help to understand the particular context of remote learning in Saudi Arabia and inform the

development of successful educational strategies and interventions during times of crisis by applying these theoretical views.

Statement of the Problem

Evaluating the efficacy of Saudi Arabia's free education system and stipend programs in the context of the COVID-19 pandemic entails investigating the impact of these initiatives on educational opportunities, reducing educational disparities, and promoting social justice during times of crisis. Due to the constraints imposed by the epidemic on person-to-person encounters, different data collection approaches must be investigated in order to answer these issues.

The social justice theory, as previously indicated, is one theoretical framework that might guide the evaluation of these projects. The ideas of fairness, equal opportunity, and resolving socioeconomic inequities in education are central to social justice philosophy. Using this hypothesis, the researchers may examine how Saudi Arabia's free education system and stipend programs help to improving educational prospects for students, especially during the pandemic. It is useful to investigate whether these activities are reaching excluded groups, minimizing educational gaps, and promoting equitable access to education.

Alternative means of data gathering, such as online surveys, virtual interviews, or data analysis, can be considered. Online surveys can collect quantifiable data about students' experiences with the free education system and stipend programs, their perceptions of the influence on their educational opportunities, and any inequities that have been observed. Virtual interviews enable researchers to acquire more in-depth qualitative data, allowing them to investigate the lived experiences and viewpoints of students, educators, and officials involved in the initiatives. Furthermore, an examination of existing statistics, such as educational attainment and enrollment

rates, might shed light on the overall impact of these programs on educational achievements in the context of the epidemic.

This study aims to evaluate the efficacy of Saudi Arabia's free education system and stipend programs in the context of the COVID-19 pandemic by incorporating social justice theory as a guiding framework and exploring alternative data collection methods such as online surveys, virtual interviews, and analysis of existing data. These methodologies enable the collection of both quantitative and qualitative data, allowing for a thorough assessment of the impact of these activities on educational opportunities, inequities reduction, and social justice promotion. Using these methodologies, the study can help to evidence-based decision-making and policy creation, ensuring that educational interventions effectively address students' needs and promote equitable access to education even in times of crisis.

Rationale

The argument for researching Saudi Arabia's education system in the context of COVID-19 goes beyond the country's immediate impact. This research has the potential to provide useful insights for educational policymakers and practitioners globally, particularly in the areas of educational equity, access, and crisis response, by assessing the impact of free education and stipend programs. This study adds to the current literature by assessing the effectiveness of these interventions in Saudi Arabia. It also informs educational practices and policies in other contexts experiencing similar issues.

Theoretical frameworks like social justice theory, the capability approach, and human capital theory provide a conceptual foundation for understanding the importance of these interventions in promoting individual development, equitable access to education, and societal progress, even in difficult circumstances. As previously said, social justice theory investigates the

ideals of fairness, equal opportunity, and eliminating social inequities in education. Using this theory, the study can assess the extent to which Saudi Arabia's free education system and stipend programs contribute to reducing educational disparities and promoting social justice during the and post COVID-19 pandemic, providing insights into effective educational equity strategies.

Amartya Sen's capability approach highlights the role of education in improving individuals' capabilities and freedoms. Using this idea, the study can show how Saudi Arabia's educational initiatives, such as free education and stipend programs, enable individuals to attain their full potential and live meaningful lives even in the face of a worldwide crisis. It is beneficial to comprehend the function of education in promoting individual growth and empowerment, which can have long-term good effects on individuals and society as a whole.

Gary Becker's human capital theory sees education as an investment in human capital that fosters economic growth and development. Using this approach, the study can investigate how Saudi Arabia's free education system and stipend programs help to the development of a professional and knowledgeable workforce, despite the COVID-19 pandemic's challenges. It aids in understanding the possible long-term benefits of investing in education, both for individuals and for the nation's overall prosperity.

Using social justice theory, the capacity approach, and human capital theory, this paper gives a comprehensive assessment of the significance of Saudi Arabia's free education system and stipend programs in the context of the post COVID-19 pandemic. These theoretical frameworks provide insights into the principles, values, and advantages connected with these educational interventions, adding to the existing literature on educational equity, access, and crisis response. Furthermore, by using these theories, the study can benefit educational policymakers and practitioners globally, providing recommendations on successful techniques for encouraging

individual growth, equal access to education, and societal advancement, even in difficult conditions.

Prior Interventions

The current study focuses on Saudi Arabia's education system and its post response to the COVID-19 pandemic, specifically policymakers' and educators' interventions and modifications. Theories of educational transformation, crisis management, and technological integration can be used to acquire insights into the dynamics of these interventions and their impact on the education system.

Michael Fullan's (2015) theory of educational transformation highlights the dynamic and multifaceted character of educational reform. This theory provides a framework for analyzing and controlling changes in educational practices and institutions. This theory can shed light on the challenges and opportunities associated with the rapid shift to online learning platforms, teacher training programs for remote instruction, and initiatives aimed at ensuring equal access to education in the context of Saudi Arabia's response to the COVID-19 pandemic. It is beneficial to investigate the elements that support or hinder the successful implementation of these reforms, as well as the tactics used to traverse the intricacies of educational reform during a crisis.

The crisis management lifecycle model, for example, can provide insights into the methods and activities used by educational policymakers and administrators to handle the issues faced by the COVID-19 pandemic. Pre-crisis, response, recuperation, and learning are common stages in this approach. The study can assess the decision-making processes, communication methods, resource allocation, and policy modifications implemented during each stage of the crisis by applying this theory. It is useful to understand how Saudi Arabia's education system dealt with the

pandemic's issues, such as the adoption of online learning platforms and measures to ensure equal access to education for all learners.

Theories of technology integration, such as the technology acceptance model (TAM), can provide insights about the uptake and use of online learning platforms and other educational technologies throughout the epidemic. TAM is concerned with people's views and attitudes toward technology, as well as the elements that influence their willingness to adopt and incorporate it into their educational practices (Marangunić & Granić, 2015). Using this theory, the study may investigate the factors that influenced educators' and students' acceptance and effective use of online learning platforms in Saudi Arabia. It aids in the identification of the hurdles and facilitators of technology integration in the educational system, as well as providing suggestions for future technology adoption and implementation.

This study presents a complete assessment of the interventions and changes undertaken by Saudi Arabia's education system in response to the post COVID-19 pandemic by merging theories of educational transformation, crisis management, and technological integration. These theoretical frameworks provide insights into the challenges, opportunities, and techniques used in the implementation of online learning platforms, teacher training programs, and equal access initiatives in education. The study's application of these theories can inform educational policymakers and practitioners about effective approaches to managing crises, navigating educational change, and integrating technology into educational practices, ultimately improving the resilience and adaptability of education systems during times of crisis.

Research Questions

Considering the challenges posed by limited person-to-person data collection post COVID-19 new normal, the study focuses on the following research questions:

1. How has Saudi Arabia's approach to stipend allocation evolved to better align with the changing educational landscape, which increasingly incorporates online and distance learning modalities?
2. What is the impact of these programs on the academic progress, personal well-being, and overall educational experience of students?

These study topics seek to investigate changes in Saudi Arabia's stipend allocation method in response to the expanding educational landscape, notably with the incorporation of online and distance learning modalities. The inquiry tries to understand how stipend programs have evolved to support students in this shifting climate. Furthermore, the study investigates the impact of these programs on other elements of students' lives, such as academic advancement, personal well-being, and overall educational experience. This analysis considers elements such as student performance, retention rates, mental health, and the overall quality of their learning journey.

Significance of the Study

The current study is significant for a wide range of stakeholders in the Saudi education system and beyond. The theoretical frameworks could help many stakeholders better understand the implications and benefits:

1. Policymakers and education authorities in Saudi Arabia
 - 1) Institutional theory can assist policymakers analyze the impact of external circumstances on the creation and execution of education programs, such as during and post COVID-19 epidemic. It underlines the significance of policies that are in line with societal expectations, norms, and values (Scott, 2008). Policymakers can use this theory to examine the success of existing free education and stipend programs in light of the crisis, and make educated decisions to optimize educational options and support mechanisms.

2) Resource dependency theory emphasizes the connection of organizations and their surroundings. Policymakers can use this theory in the context of this study to examine resource availability and allocation, collaborations with external stakeholders, and the influence of resource restrictions on the execution of educational programs during the pandemic (Salancik, 1978).

2. Educators and practitioners

1) The community of inquiry paradigm developed by Garrison *et al.* (2000) can provide insights into effective teaching and learning practices in online and remote education. This approach highlights the role of cognitive presence, social presence, and teaching presence in producing engaging and meaningful learning experiences. Educators can use this idea to improve their instructional practices, encourage student interaction and cooperation, and promote inclusive and equitable learning environments during times of limited face-to-face interaction.

2) Deci and Ryan (2000) created a theory of self-determination that focuses on intrinsic motivation and the satisfaction of basic psychological needs. Educators can use this theory to better understand how free education and stipend programs can increase students' autonomy, competence, and relatedness, hence increasing motivation and engagement in online learning environments.

3. International students considering educational opportunities in Saudi Arabia

Social capital theory can assist overseas students in evaluating the benefits of studying in Saudi Arabia as well as the existing support mechanisms, such as stipend programs. This theory highlights the importance of social networks, relationships, and resources in gaining access to opportunities and obtaining positive outcomes (Richardson & Bourdieu, 1986;

Dubos, 2017). During a global crisis, international students can use this theory to analyze the potential social and academic support they may receive, increasing their academic experiences and future career opportunities.

4. Researchers and scholars

The study adds to the field of crisis-responsive education policies and practices, and scholars can use the findings to inform their own work. The earlier described theoretical frameworks, such as institutional theory, resource dependency theory, the community of inquiry framework, and social capital theory, can serve as a foundation for future research in similar circumstances or when evaluating the impact of educational interventions during crises. Researchers can use these ideas to delve deeper into the dynamics of educational transformation, crisis management, and technology integration in various contexts.

Policymakers, educators, international students, and researchers can acquire significant insights from the study's findings and apply them to their particular areas by considering these theoretical viewpoints. This research has the potential to influence policy decisions, improve instructional methods, support international students in making decisions, and contribute to the larger knowledge base on crisis-responsive education policies and practices.

This study intends to look into the generosity of Saudi Arabia's education system by studying the provision of free education and stipend programs in the context of during and post COVID-19 pandemic. This study seeks to contribute to understanding of educational practices and policies, as well as their impact on educational access, equity, and student outcomes during times of crisis by applying relevant theoretical frameworks and adapting data collection methods to address the limitations of person-to-person interaction. The findings of this study will have ramifications for educational policymakers, practitioners, international students, and researchers,

providing vital insights into effective strategies and support mechanisms in the face of global problems.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Education, a cornerstone of human civilization, transcends mere instruction to encompass a holistic journey of personal and societal development. Rooted in ancient civilizations' oral traditions and apprenticeships, education has evolved into a sophisticated system tailored to meet diverse individual and societal needs. Its significance is underscored by a myriad of theories, including Piaget's constructivism (1972), Vygotsky's sociocultural theory (1978), and Maslow's hierarchy of needs (1969), which elucidate its profound impact on human development. Piaget's constructivism posits that individuals actively construct knowledge through experiences, while Vygotsky's sociocultural theory emphasizes the role of social interaction and cultural context in shaping learning. Maslow's hierarchy highlights education's role in fulfilling basic needs and fostering self-actualization. These theories converge to underscore education's pivotal role in equipping individuals with cognitive, social, and emotional competencies essential for personal fulfillment and societal progress.

Moreover, education's enduring importance is evident in its ability to address contemporary challenges and opportunities. In today's knowledge-based economy, education is not merely a pathway to employment but a catalyst for innovation, critical thinking, and lifelong learning. As technological advancements reshape industries and labor markets, education equips individuals with the skills and adaptability needed to thrive in a dynamic world. Furthermore, education promotes social cohesion and equity by providing equal access to opportunities and fostering empathy and understanding across diverse communities.

The influence of Saudi Arabia's free education system and stipend programs on educational access, equity, and student outcomes is investigated in this literature review. The article aims to provide insights into the alignment of these initiatives with social justice principles, the

empowerment of individuals through the capability approach, and their contribution to human capital development and economic growth as viewed through human capital theory by analyzing relevant studies and literature. This assessment also takes into account other elements that determine the performance of these programs, such as technology, teacher quality, and curriculum design.

The article investigates the connection between Saudi Arabia's educational endeavors and social justice, emphasizing how the free education system and stipend programs attempt to minimize gaps and give equitable access to education. Additionally, it focuses on the capacity approach and human capital theory, exploring how these theoretical frameworks give a lens through which to view individual empowerment and the role of education in economic development. Furthermore, the review recognizes the significance of other factors such as technology, teacher quality, and curriculum design in shaping educational access, equity, and student outcomes in Saudi Arabia.

Social Justice Theory and Its Relevance to Education: Fostering Equity and Inclusion

Social justice theory is important in developing educational practices and policies with the goal of creating a fair and inclusive society by eliminating systematic disparities and fostering equitable chances for all people. This section dives into social justice theory and its use in education. Individuals will get a better knowledge of how social justice theory impacts educational practices, policies, and outcomes by investigating both classic and modern perspectives.

The Concept of Social Justice Theory

The ideas of fairness, equality, and the abolition of societal injustices are central to social justice theory (Rawls, 1971). In the context of education, it emphasizes ensuring equitable access to quality education for all individuals, regardless of their background or circumstances. This

viewpoint acknowledges that socioeconomic position, race, or gender should not dictate educational chances.

Classic Theories:

1. **John Rawls' Theory of Justice:** Rawls proposed the concept of justice as fairness, stating that a just society should ensure that all persons have equal access to resources, including education (Rawls, 1971). Rawls' theory serves as a foundation for comprehending the significance of fair educational opportunities in promoting social justice.
2. **Paulo Freire's Critical Pedagogy:** Freire's critical pedagogy stresses the empowerment of oppressed individuals via education (Freire, 1970). It emphasizes the importance of educators critically examining power relations and challenging oppressive institutions in the educational system in order to liberate learners from social injustices.

Modern Theories:

1. **Nancy Fraser's Theory of Social Justice:** In her theory of social justice, Fraser emphasizes the significance of acknowledgment and redistribution (Fraser, 2014). Recognizing and appreciating individuals' different identities and experiences within the educational system is referred to as recognition, whereas redistribution addresses the unequal allocation of resources.
2. **Critical Race Theory:** Critical Race Theory investigates the relationship between race and education, with the goal of exposing and challenging structural racism in educational institutions (Ladson-Billings, 2020). It emphasizes the need of addressing racial inequities and creating inclusive educational settings that validate and empower children of all races.

Relevance to Education

Social justice theory is important in education because it helps educators, policymakers, and organizations promote equity, inclusivity, and social change. The following benefits can be accomplished by implementing social justice ideals into educational practices and policies:

1. **Equal Access:** According to social justice theory, everyone should have equal access to a good education, regardless of their background or social standing. This method assures that all children have access to educational resources, opportunities, and support networks, hence closing the achievement gap (Darling-Hammond, 2015).
2. **Inclusive Curriculum:** According to social justice theory, inclusive curriculum should reflect students' diverse backgrounds, experiences, and cultures (Banks, 2015). Incorporating multiple viewpoints and tales builds a sense of belonging while also encouraging critical thinking and empathy in students.
3. **Empowerment and Agency:** By incorporating social justice ideals into education, students can be empowered to become active agents of change. It promotes critical thinking by assisting students in recognizing and challenging social inequalities in their communities (Giroux, 2007).

Social justice theory offers a framework for tackling systemic inequities and fostering fairness and inclusivity in education. Educators and policymakers can work to create educational systems that prioritize equity, access, and empowerment of all individuals by drawing on classic theories such as Rawls' concept of justice as fairness and Freire's critical pedagogy, as well as modern theories such as Fraser's theory of social justice and Critical Race Theory. Education becomes a powerful tool for building a just and equitable society when it embraces social justice ideas.

Promoting Social Justice through Saudi Arabia's Education System: An Analysis of Former and Recent Reforms

Saudi Arabia's education system has seen considerable changes throughout the years, with a focus on achieving social justice. This section investigates how the Kingdom's former and contemporary education systems accord with social justice concepts. We can examine the efficacy of these activities on promoting fair access to education and reducing socioeconomic gaps by evaluating the evolution of Saudi Arabia's educational policies. Classic theories, such as John Rawls' Theory of Justice as Fairness, and modern theories, such as Amartya Sen's Capability Approach, will be integrated to provide a comprehensive understanding of Saudi Arabia's educational reforms and social justice principles (Rawls, 1971; Sen, 2000).

The Former Education System

Saudi Arabia has always encountered difficulties in maintaining equitable access to education, particularly among underprivileged people. The scarcity of schools and educational resources reduced many people's accesses to education, resulting in gender inequities and limited access for women (Alkhazim, 2003). During this time period, however, efforts were undertaken to build educational institutions and provide basic education.

Classic theories of social justice can still be used, notwithstanding the constraints of the previous schooling system. The Theory of Justice as Fairness proposed by John Rawls emphasizes the necessity of fair opportunities for all members of society. While the previous system fell short of these aspirations, it did provide the framework for future improvements that adhere to social justice ideas (Rawls, 1971).

Recent Education Reforms

Saudi Arabia has made great progress in recent years to modernize its education system and promote social fairness. Comprehensive reforms emphasizing curriculum development, teacher training, and infrastructural enhancement have been implemented (Mitchell & Alfuraih, 2018; Broer *et al.*, 2019). These changes seek to improve educational quality, increase access to education, and reduce socioeconomic inequality.

Amartya Sen's Capability Approach is relevant to comprehending Saudi Arabia's current reforms. This approach emphasizes the significance of education in broadening people's skills and liberties. Saudi Arabia's latest education reforms aim to improve students' capabilities by expanding their knowledge, skills, and opportunities (Sen, 2000).

Alignment with Principles of Social Justice

Saudi Arabia's recent education reforms exhibit a strong affinity with social justice ideas. Access to education has been improved for all elements of society, including traditionally marginalized populations. School development, the introduction of remote learning programs, and the formation of scholarships have all increased educational opportunities (Alkhazim, 2003). Gender equality in education has also been a priority, with policies and programs targeted at increasing female enrollment and correcting gender imbalances (Singh *et al.*, 2022; Hamdan & Hamdan, 2020, Baki, 2004).

Education in Saudi Arabia: A Comprehensive Overview

Saudi Arabia prioritizes public education, allocating 8.8% of its GDP to the field, about double the worldwide average. The educational system is comprehensive, encompassing Islamic, scientific, and social disciplines, with a strong emphasis on Islamic studies. On average, key disciplines such as mathematics, science, social studies, languages, and physical education receive around 23 periods per week. Since the inception of King Saud University in 1957, the Saudi

educational system has undergone considerable changes. Notably, the landscape has shifted to accommodate a sizable proportion of female university graduates. Despite previous criticisms about teacher training, retention rates, and scientific instruction, the system has developed and is today recognized for providing quality education across multiple disciplines.

The education system is overseen by the Ministry of Education, in collaboration with the TVTC, and is assisted by other authorities. The Supreme Committee for Educational Policy is the highest level of supervision. Saudi Arabia devotes 6.8% of its GDP to education, demonstrating its dedication. The Ministry of Education has developed a comprehensive ten-year plan that focuses on improving several aspects of the system, including early childhood education, comprehensive education, technical education for girls, and more.

Advancements and Challenges in Women's and Gifted Education

Meanwhile, Saudi Arabia has made significant progress in women's education and the development of gifted education programs in recent years. Despite obstacles, progress in these areas demonstrates the country's dedication to developing a varied and inclusive educational landscape. The opening of private girls' schools in Jeddah in 1957 was a watershed moment, heralding a gradual increase in university prospects for women by the late 1970s. Saudi females now account for 60% of university students in the country, exceeding neighboring countries. Efforts to address the gender wage disparity in the labor force are ongoing.

The interest in gifted education stretches back to 1969, when specialist schools and enrichment programs were established. The requirement for an appropriate curriculum, differentiation in normal classrooms, and combating negative teacher attitudes are all ongoing challenges. Gifted students are defined in Saudi Arabia as those with outstanding skills who require specialized educational care, with an emphasis on individualized instruction, peer interaction,

responsive parents, and empathic supervision. The Mawhiba Talented Program is critical in identifying and developing talented learners, maximizing their potential, and contributing to the development of extraordinary individuals who make major social contributions.

Higher Education Landscape and Ongoing Reforms

Higher education in Saudi Arabia has received tremendous investment, spanning four years for humanities and social sciences and five to six years for professions such as medicine and engineering. The establishment of King Saud University in 1957 heralded the beginning of modern higher education in the region. The country currently has 24 government universities, which are supplemented by private colleges, community colleges, and specialized institutions. Since its inception in 2005, the government's scholarship program has assisted Saudi students' foreign studies in nations such as the United States, the United Kingdom, Canada, and Australia.

To support scientific research and development, the country promotes research capacity and innovation, building research centers, institutes, and science parks. Collaborations with international universities have been fostered in order to improve information exchange and research outcomes. Curriculum changes, teacher training, and accreditation processes are all ongoing efforts to improve education and link it with global labor market demands. Investment in infrastructure and online learning platforms has also embraced digital revolution. Saudi Arabia's dedication to education is seen in its extensive and modern education system, which addresses difficulties, fosters inclusion, and embraces technology innovations.

Moreover, Saudi Arabia recognizes the importance of meeting the different educational demands of its expatriate groups. Diplomatic missions and private efforts impact international education in the country, offering a diversity of curricula and catering to diverse nationalities. There are two types of international schools: foreign schools and community-based schools.

Foreign schools use curricula that differ from the Saudi national curriculum, whereas community-based schools, which are administered by diplomatic missions, primarily serve certain ethnicities.

The International Schools Statute, enacted by the Saudi Ministry of Education, governs international schools. Certain exemptions apply to community-based schools controlled by diplomatic missions, whereas private foreign schools must follow Saudi laws. Community-based schools that serve certain nationalities follow the curricula of their respective nations, enabling a mixed-gender learning environment. Recognizing the function of diplomatic missions, the Saudi Ministry of Education regulates community schools with discretion. Saudi restrictions, including gender segregation, must be followed by private foreign schools in Saudi Arabia. The number of private schools permitted per nationality fluctuates according on Saudi nationals' desire in founding schools in a specific city.

The Ministry of Investment and the Royal Commission for Riyadh City cooperated with SEK Education Group to create SEK International School Riyadh in July 2021. The school seeks to provide an innovative, multilingual, and English-based environment and is accredited to teach the International Baccalaureate (IB) Primary Years Programme (PYP), Middle Years Programme (MYP), and Diploma Programme (DP). This relationship expands Saudi Arabia's educational alternatives, contributing to a dynamic and inclusive learning environment. The educational scene in Saudi Arabia displays a commitment to inclusion, innovation, and global engagement. The country is on a constant improvement path, from emphasizing public education to tackling gender disparities, developing gifted students, and embracing international education. Ongoing reforms and strategic initiatives demonstrate Saudi Arabia's commitment to establishing a comprehensive and contemporary education system that prepares its citizens for future challenges and possibilities.

Saudi Arabia's Extensive Education System

The astounding number of schools created across Saudi Arabia demonstrates the country's dedication to education. The Kingdom had 38,150 schools as of 2019, a 16.5% growth since 2015. This significant growth demonstrates Saudi Arabia's commitment to improving access to education throughout the country and resolving historical issues connected with limited educational possibilities (Alkhazim, 2003; Alotaibi, 2023).

Furthermore, the large number of schools demonstrates the government's dedication to supporting its population's educational demands. Significant investments have been made in the construction of new schools, the improvement of infrastructure, and the improvement of the overall quality of education supplied to children (Mitchell & Alfuraih, 2018). When the number of schools in Saudi Arabia is compared to that of other affluent countries, it is clear that the Kingdom has achieved great success in extending its educational infrastructure. Despite its small population in comparison to other industrialized countries, the vast number of schools in Saudi Arabia demonstrates the country's commitment to making education accessible to its inhabitants in accordance with social justice principles (Alkhazim, 2003).

Saudi Arabia's educational system has grown significantly becoming increasingly aligned with social justice ideas. Recent changes have placed a premium on ensuring equitable access to education, reducing socioeconomic inequities, and fostering gender equality. While the former education system had difficulties attaining social equity goals, it laid the groundwork for the substantial reforms adopted in recent years. Saudi Arabia's education system continues to progress toward establishing a more equitable and inclusive society by incorporating both classic notions of justice such as fairness and newer theories such as the capabilities approach.

Impact of Educational Initiatives on Enhancing Access and Reducing Disparities in Saudi Arabia: A Comprehensive Review

Education is critical in fostering social justice and decreasing socioeconomic inequality. Significant attempts have been launched in Saudi Arabia to improve educational access and alleviate inequities among various groups of the population. This article includes a thorough examination of studies and research that investigate the impact of various measures on improving educational access and reducing inequities in Saudi Arabia. We can acquire a better understanding of the effectiveness of these programs and their conformity with classic and modern notions of social justice by studying the findings of these research.

John Rawls' Theory of Justice as Fairness promotes equitable chances for all members of society (Rawls, 1971). This theory provides a framework for evaluating the impact of educational efforts in Saudi Arabia, emphasizing the necessity of fair access to education. We may analyze their consistency with the concepts of justice as fairness by looking at how these programs have improved educational access across different social and economic backgrounds.

Amartya Sen's Capability Approach (Sen, 2000) focuses on increasing individuals' capacities and freedoms through education. This idea provides a lens through which we can examine how educational programs in Saudi Arabia have improved individuals' talents, skills, and opportunities. We may examine their alignment with the principles of the capacity approach by assessing the larger impact of these activities on persons' well-being and empowerment.

Impact on Educational Access

Numerous studies have been conducted to investigate the impact of educational efforts on increasing access to education in Saudi Arabia. Singh *et al.* (2022), for example, did research on

the function of the Saudi education system in fostering gender equality. The findings demonstrated that measures aimed at increasing female enrollment and resolving gender inequities considerably enhanced girls' and women's access to education.

Alkhazim (2003) also performed research on the difficulties and solutions in the Saudi education system. The report emphasized several steps implemented to increase educational access, such as school construction, the introduction of online learning programs, and the distribution of scholarships. These projects have been critical in increasing access to education, particularly among underprivileged groups.

Impact on Reducing Disparities

The influence of educational programs on eliminating inequities in Saudi Arabia has also been studied. Mitchell & Alfuraih (2018) did research on the importance of educational reform in attaining Saudi Arabia's Vision 2030 development plan. According to the report, significant reforms aimed at curriculum creation, teacher training, and infrastructure enhancement have helped to reduce gaps in educational quality and resources across the country.

Furthermore, Alkhazim (2003) found that initiatives to expand educational access had helped minimize socioeconomic disparities. These programs have played a critical role in promoting social justice and minimizing inequities in educational attainment by giving educational opportunities to individuals from varied socioeconomic backgrounds. Various studies and research have demonstrated that actions implemented in Saudi Arabia to promote educational access and minimize inequality have had a major impact. These programs accord with conventional ideas of justice as fairness, such as John Rawls' Theory, by promoting equitable chances for all members of society. They also align with modern perspectives, such as Amartya Sen's Capability Approach, in that education improves individuals' skills and freedoms.

These initiatives have enhanced access to education for historically underrepresented populations, particularly females, through the creation of schools, distance learning programs, scholarships, and overall reforms. They have also helped to reduce inequities in educational quality and resources between regions and socioeconomic groups. Saudi Arabia may improve educational access and minimize disparities by continuously reviewing the efficacy of these measures and connecting them with social justice ideas, thereby promoting a more fair and inclusive society.

The Capability Approach: Empowering Individuals through Capacities and Freedoms

The capabilities approach has received a lot of attention in the field of social justice. The capacity method, developed by Nobel laureate Amartya Sen, provides a comprehensive framework for assessing well-being and assessing societal progress. This article goes into the capability approach concept, studying its key tenets and emphasizing its emphasis on individuals' talents and freedoms. We can obtain a better grasp of the importance of this method in fostering social justice and human development by investigating the classic and modern theories that underpin it.

The Capability Approach: A Comprehensive Perspective

The capabilities approach has received a lot of attention in the field of social justice. The capacity method, developed by Nobel laureate Amartya Sen, provides a comprehensive framework for assessing well-being and assessing societal progress. This article goes into the capability approach concept, studying its key tenets and emphasizing its emphasis on individuals' talents and freedoms. We can obtain a better grasp of the importance of this method in fostering social justice and human development by investigating the classic and modern theories that underpin it.

Classic Theory: Aristotle's Theory of Human Flourishing

The capacity approach is influenced by a number of classic philosophies, notably Aristotle's theory of human flourishing. According to Aristotle (Segvic. 2002), the ultimate

objective of human life is to achieve eudaimonia, a condition of thriving and well-being. Aristotle's philosophy, like the capacity approach, highlights the importance of capabilities and functioning, emphasizing on the development and exercise of human capacities for a fulfilling life.

Modern Theory: John Rawls' Theory of Justice as Fairness

The Theory of Justice as Fairness by John Rawls is equally relevant to the capacity approach. Rawls advocated that justice should emphasize the well-being of society's most vulnerable people (Rawls, 1971). This is consistent with the capacity approach's emphasis on improving people's capacities and freedoms, particularly those who are excluded or disadvantaged. Both ideas emphasize the importance of addressing social, economic, and political inequities in order to create a just society.

The Focus on Capacities and Freedoms

The capacity approach emphasizes people' capacities and freedoms. It recognizes that people have different objectives, values, and aspirations, and that their ability to attain what they value influences their well-being. The capacity method evaluates a person's freedom to live a life they value by analyzing their capabilities — their effective opportunities to do and be what they want.

Furthermore, the concept understands that many elements, such as social, economic, and political contexts, influence talents. It emphasizes the significance of removing impediments to individuals' development and limiting their freedoms. Societies can build an enabling environment that encourages human flourishing by extending people's potential through education, healthcare, access to resources, and participation opportunities.

The Evaluation of Well-being and Development

The capacity approach provides a comprehensive view of happiness and growth. It takes into account a variety of criteria such as education, health, work, political participation, social ties, and personal security. The approach gives a comprehensive evaluation of people's well-being beyond traditional statistics such as income or GDP by analyzing these dimensions. The capacity approach acknowledges that people's freedoms and capabilities are intertwined, generating a complex web of impacts. Improving one skill can have a positive ripple effect on other areas of life, resulting in a more holistic and long-term improvement in well-being.

Amartya Sen's capacity approach provides a useful framework for assessing social justice and well-being. The method gives a holistic view of human development by moving the focus from results to individuals' talents and freedoms. The capacity approach emphasizes the significance of strengthening people's skills to lead lives they value, drawing inspiration from traditional theories such as Aristotle's conception of human flourishing and aligning with modern theories such as Rawls' conception of Justice as Fairness.

The capacity approach, with its emphasis on capacities and freedoms, provides a lens through which nations can examine and address disparities, empower marginalized groups, and promote social justice. The capacity approach is a helpful tool in creating a more equal and flourishing society by extending opportunities, removing barriers, and establishing an inclusive and enabling environment.

Empowering Through Education: Analyzing Saudi Arabia's Educational Initiatives and their Impact on Enhancing Individuals' Capabilities

Education is critical in empowering individuals, broadening their talents, and promoting social and economic progress. Saudi Arabia has made tremendous progress in adopting educational initiatives aimed at improving people's talents and empowering them to live fulfilled lives. This

article digs into an examination of Saudi Arabia's educational efforts, examining how they contribute to the development of individuals' capacities and empowerment. Individuals can get insights into the underlying concepts and impacts of these activities by studying relevant theories.

The Capability Approach: Empowerment through Capabilities

Amartya Sen's capabilities approach provides a useful foundation for examining Saudi Arabia's educational endeavors. This approach highlights the importance of increasing people's capabilities, which are the effective freedoms they have to live the lives they want (Sen, 2000). Saudi Arabia seeks to empower individuals by improving educational opportunities and giving them with the skills, knowledge, and resources they need to exercise their choices and live meaningful lives.

Human Capital Theory: Investing in Capabilities

The human capital theory provides another perspective on the influence of Saudi Arabia's educational endeavors. According to Schultz (1961), education is an investment in individuals' capacities that leads to improved production, economic prosperity, and social well-being. Saudi Arabia aims to provide its population with the human capital they need to prosper in an increasingly knowledge-driven global economy by investing in education.

Impact on Enhancing Capabilities

Saudi Arabia's educational endeavors have significantly improved citizens' talents. The King Abdullah Scholarship Program (KASP) is one notable effort that gives fully paid scholarships for Saudi students to pursue higher education overseas (Allmnakrah & Evers, 2020). Saudi students have access to world-class educational institutions through KASP, expanding their knowledge, talents, and perspectives. This exposure expands their intellectual powers, improves critical thinking skills, and fosters global awareness.

Furthermore, Saudi Arabia has undertaken steps to increase the country's educational quality and accessibility. Curriculum reforms have been adopted, teacher training has been invested in, and state-of-the-art educational facilities have been built by the Ministry of Education (Allmnakrah & Evers, 2020). These projects seek to improve Saudi students' capacities by providing them with a well-rounded education that prepares them for the difficulties of the modern world.

Impact on Empowerment

Individual empowerment is also aided by Saudi Arabia's educational efforts. Saudi Arabia fosters gender equality and empowers individuals by extending educational possibilities, particularly for historically marginalized groups such as women. Women's driving privileges have been restored, and women-only universities have been established, as examples of programs that empower women by providing them with greater mobility and educational opportunities (Sani, 2018; van Geel, 2016).

Furthermore, Saudi Arabia's emphasis on vocational and technical education and training (TVET) provides individuals with practical skills and knowledge, improving employability and economic empowerment (Allmnakrah & Evers, 2020). TVET programs equip individuals with the skills needed to work in a variety of industries, thereby contributing to economic growth and lowering unemployment rates. Saudi Arabia's educational efforts highlight the country's dedication to improving people's talents and encouraging empowerment. These projects attempt to provide individuals with the skills, information, and resources they need to live satisfying lives and contribute to society by harmonizing with theories such as the capability approach and the human capital theory.

Saudi Arabia improves individuals' capacities by offering access to quality education and global possibilities through initiatives such as the King Abdullah Scholarship Program, curriculum revisions, and investments in educational infrastructure. These efforts also strengthen historically marginalized populations, such as women, by increasing educational access and advocating for gender equality. Saudi Arabia can strengthen individuals' talents, create empowerment, and contribute to the nation's social and economic progress by continuously reviewing and upgrading these educational efforts.

Empowering Students: Examining the Effects of Educational Initiatives on Agency and Empowerment

Educational programs have the potential to empower students by increasing their agency—their ability to make decisions and take action—and cultivating a general sense of empowerment. This article looks at empirical facts and studies that give light on how educational efforts affect students' empowerment and agency. We can acquire insights into the transformative impact of such activities on students' lives by evaluating these studies and comparing them to relevant ideas.

Theoretical Framework: Self-Determination Theory

SDT provides a suitable theoretical framework for understanding the effects of educational activities on student empowerment. Individuals have fundamental psychological requirements for autonomy, competence, and relatedness, according to SDT (Ryan & Deci, 2000). When these requirements are met in the context of school, students enjoy increased motivation, well-being, and a sense of agency and empowerment.

Effects on Students' Empowerment and Agency:

1. **Increased Self-Efficacy:** Educational programs that give students opportunity to develop and demonstrate their talents and abilities can boost their self-efficacy (Bandura & Freeman, 1997).

Zimmerman and Schunk (2001) discovered that efforts such as project-based learning and experiential programs raised students' self-efficacy, resulting in increased agency and empowerment.

2. **Improved Decision-Making abilities:** Educational initiatives that promote active learning, critical thinking, and problem-solving abilities can empower students by providing them with the knowledge they need to make sound decisions. According to a study conducted by Mager & Nowak (2021), students who participated in programs stressing decision-making abilities reported increased levels of empowerment and agency.
3. **Increased Autonomy and Voice:** Initiatives that foster an inclusive and supportive educational atmosphere can help students gain autonomy and a say in decision-making processes. According to a study conducted by Vansteenkiste *et al.* (2004), when students' autonomy is supported, they express higher levels of empowerment and agency, which leads to increased engagement and academic success.
4. **Fostered Sense of Belonging:** Educational activities that promote a sense of belonging, such as mentorship programs and collaborative learning experiences, can have a substantial impact on students' empowerment. According to Osterman (2000), when students feel linked to their educational community, they acquire a stronger feeling of agency and empowerment, which leads to better academic achievements.
5. **Increased Participation Opportunities:** Initiatives that allow students to actively participate in decision-making and community engagement can boost their feeling of agency. Christens (2012) discovered that when students participate in participatory efforts like student councils or community service projects, they feel more empowered and have a greater sense of personal agency.

Studies and empirical evidence show that educational initiatives have a transforming impact on students' empowerment and agency. These efforts increase students' self-efficacy, decision-making abilities, autonomy, sense of belonging, and participation possibilities by harmonizing with theories such as Self-Determination Theory. As a result, students feel more empowered, motivated, and satisfied with their education.

To optimize the impact of educational efforts on student empowerment, educators and policymakers should prioritize inclusive and supportive settings, active learning, and opportunities for student voice and engagement. Educational institutions can continue to empower students by cultivating their agency and allowing them to prosper academically, personally, and socially in this way.

Human Capital Theory: Education as an Investment in Skills and Productivity

Human capital theory is a fundamental economic concept that emphasizes the value of education as an investment in individuals' talents and production. Individuals' knowledge, skills, and abilities, according to this notion, add to their overall human capital, which determines their economic success and societal contributions. In this article, we will look at human capital theory, its historical foundations, and its current relevance in society. We can obtain a full grasp of the importance of education as an investment in individuals' potential by reviewing ancient and modern theories connected to human capital.

Classic Theory: The Human Capital Theory by Gary Becker

Gary Becker's pioneering work in economics set the groundwork for human capital theory. Becker stressed in his seminal book "Human Capital: A Theoretical and Empirical Analysis with Special Reference to Education" (2009) that education is an investment that increases an individual's productivity and earning potential. Individuals allocate resources, such as time and

money, to acquire education and training, thereby expanding their human capital and enhancing their economic outcomes, according to Becker.

According to Becker's argument, education is not just a way of acquiring knowledge, but also a sort of investment in one's own skills and potential. Individuals who obtain an education increase their productivity and become more valuable assets in the job market, resulting in higher salaries and improved economic well-being.

Modern Theory: Skill-Biased Technological Change

Within human capital theory, the concept of skill-biased technological transformation has gained importance in recent decades. According to this idea, technological developments and automation favor persons with greater levels of education and specialized abilities (Acemoglu, 2002). Individuals with greater levels of education and appropriate skills are better suited to adapt and succeed in a changing labor market as technology continues to transform industries and the nature of work.

Skill-biased technological transformation emphasizes the value of education as an investment that not only increases individual productivity but also allows them to compete in an increasingly knowledge-based economy. Individuals with higher levels of education are more likely to have the skills required to capitalize on technology breakthroughs, resulting in better employment rates and economic growth.

Relevance in Modern Society

Human capital theory is still very relevant in current culture for a variety of reasons. To begin, the quick rate of technology advancement necessitates persons constantly updating their skills and knowledge in order to remain employable. Lifelong learning has become critical for remaining competitive and adjusting to changing employment demands. Second, as countries

transition from manufacturing to service-oriented and knowledge-based sectors, there is a greater demand for highly skilled personnel. Education is critical in developing a trained workforce capable of satisfying the demands of various industries.

Third, education is more than just conventional schooling; it also encompasses vocational training, professional development programs, and opportunities for continual learning. Human capital includes both traditional academic education and the learning of practical skills, ensuring that individuals have a varied range of talents that fit with labor market needs. Human capital theory emphasizes the importance of education as an investment in people's talents and output. It emphasizes that education goes beyond knowledge acquisition and is a means of improving individuals' human capital, resulting in enhanced economic outcomes and society benefits.

Classic theories, such as Gary Becker's human capital theory, established the groundwork for comprehending the relationship between education, skills, and economic success. Modern ideas, such as skill-biased technological transformation, acknowledge the changing character of the labor market as well as the growing necessity of education in responding to technology innovations. Education remains a valuable asset in today's knowledge-based economy for those looking to improve their capabilities, increase their employability, and contribute to economic progress. Societies may prioritize and support educational opportunities that empower individuals and drive societal progress by considering education as an investment in human capital.

Saudi Arabia's Islamic Approach to Free Education and Equitable Student Support

Programmes

Looking at the state viewpoint, since Saudi Arabia is a major Muslim country, it is vital to revisit the importance of education from an Islamic perspective as the fundamental pillar of the Saudi state and its society.

Unlocking Divine Wisdom: The Importance of Education in Islam

Education is vital to Islam, not just as a secular pursuit, but also as a spiritual requirement and method of attaining heavenly knowledge. The Quran and Hadith provide profound insights on the importance of education, encouraging believers to pursue knowledge and wisdom in all areas of life. One of the most famous verses in the Quran is Surah Al-Alaq (96:1-5), in which Allah tells the Prophet Muhammad (peace be upon him) to "Read! In the name of your Lord who created...". This verse emphasizes the divine necessity to seek knowledge by reading and studying, highlighting the fundamental significance of education in Islam.

Education, according to Islamic thought, is a lifetime journey of knowledge and personal progress. The Prophet Muhammad (peace be upon him) highlighted the value of knowledge, saying, "Seeking knowledge is obligatory upon every Muslim" (Al-Tirmidhi). This directive emphasizes the idea that education is more than a choice; it is a religious duty that all believers must fulfill.

In addition, education in Islam is not limited to religious subjects but includes a wide range of fields such as physics, mathematics, literature, and ethics. The Quran encourages believers to consider the signs of Allah's creation and to study the secrets of the universe. This holistic approach to teaching encourages critical thinking, intellectual curiosity, and a deep respect for nature's beauties.

Furthermore, education is viewed as a tool for promoting social justice and equality in Islamic civilizations. The Prophet Muhammad (peace be upon him) famously stated that "the seeking of knowledge is obligatory for every Muslim" (Ibn Majah), emphasizing the egalitarian aspect of education in Islam. Education promotes social mobility, economic prosperity, and community development by equipping individuals with knowledge and skills.

In contemporary society, governments have a crucial role to play in promoting education and ensuring universal access to quality schooling. This entails investing in educational infrastructure, teacher training, curriculum development, and educational technology. Additionally, governments must implement policies that promote inclusive education, gender equality, and lifelong learning opportunities for all citizens. Education is extremely important in Islam as a religious requirement, a means of enlightenment, and a catalyst for social change. Prioritizing education allows communities to empower individuals to reach their greatest potential, fosters a culture of learning and inquiry, and creates a brighter future for future generations.

Saudi Arabia's Comprehensive Approach to Free Education and Student Support Programs

Meanwhile, education is a cornerstone of progress and development in any society. In Saudi Arabia, a country profoundly steeped in Islamic beliefs, education is more than just a way of acquiring knowledge; it is a fundamental right and duty given on each individual. The Kingdom's commitment to providing free education systems and extensive student support programs reflects its desire to cultivate a culture of learning, equity, and excellence.

Islamic teachings emphasize the necessity of acquiring knowledge as a fundamental duty for all Muslims. The Quran extols the benefits of knowledge and enlightenment, with countless passages encouraging believers to think, ask, and obtain wisdom. The Prophet Muhammad (peace be upon him) highlighted the importance of education, saying, "Seeking knowledge is obligatory upon every Muslim" (Sunan Ibn Majah). Thus, Saudi Arabia's educational efforts are profoundly anchored in Islamic beliefs, which regard education not just as a secular pursuit but also as a spiritual obligation and path to enlightenment.

Saudi Arabia has adopted comprehensive free education systems from the basic to the tertiary levels, in accordance with its commitment to Islamic justice and equality. This program assures that no segment of society is denied access to high-quality education because of budgetary concerns. Students across the Kingdom, regardless of socioeconomic status or geographical location, are given equal opportunity to pursue their educational goals. Furthermore, the government's investment in educational infrastructure, including as schools, colleges, and universities, makes learning more accessible in both urban and rural locations.

Saudi Arabia emphasizes the need of achieving educational parity so that every individual can reach their full potential. To address inequities and close access gaps, the government has launched focused efforts and allocated resources. Underserved communities, notably those in distant places and marginalized groups, get special attention to ensure adequate support and resources. Additionally, initiatives focused at empowering students with impairments exist to encourage inclusivity and remove barriers to learning.

Beyond access and equity, Saudi Arabia is dedicated to improving student learning outcomes through extensive support programs. These programs cover a wide range of efforts, including financial help, academic support, and career advising. Notably, the government gives students with various allowances to help them pay for educational expenditures including as tuition, textbooks, and transportation. These initiatives allow students and their families to focus on their academics and reach their full academic potential by relieving financial burdens.

To sum up, Saudi Arabia's commitment to free education systems and extensive student support programs demonstrates its commitment to encouraging access to education, equity, and success. These efforts, based on Islamic principles of knowledge and justice, demonstrate the Kingdom's unshakable commitment to creating a society in which education is not simply a

privilege but a fundamental right for all. Saudi Arabia's continued investment in human capital through education sets the way for a more prosperous, enlightened, and socially cohesive future.

Saudi Arabia's Free Education System and Stipend Programs: Fostering a Knowledgeable Workforce for Economic Growth

Saudi Arabia's commitment to free education and stipend programs reflects the country's goal of developing an informed and talented workforce capable of driving economic progress. In this article, it's important to look at how Saudi Arabia's free education system and stipend programs help to develop human capital and how they affect the country's economic prosperity. We may acquire a full grasp of the significance of these programs in Saudi Arabia's pursuit of a competent workforce by investigating relevant theories and empirical facts.

Investing in Human Capital: The Significance of Education

Human capital theory, as espoused by economists such as Gary Becker, emphasizes education's significance as an investment in individuals' skills and talents (Becker, 2009). Saudi Arabia emphasizes the importance of education in generating a skilled workforce capable of driving economic progress. By providing free education, the country ensures that all citizens have access to high-quality education, allowing them to gain the information and skills needed to contribute to the nation's progress.

Saudi Arabia's Free Education System

Saudi Arabia's publicly funded educational system includes primary, secondary, and tertiary levels. The Ministry of Education oversees the system, concentrating on enhancing educational quality, extending access, and aligning curricula with labor market demands. The free education system not only encourages equal opportunity, but it also builds a knowledgeable workforce by offering a solid foundation of academic and technical skills.

The government heavily invests in primary and secondary education, providing free education to all Saudi nationals. This ensures that youngsters obtain a well-rounded education and begin to acquire important abilities at a young age. The curriculum focuses on Arabic, Islamic studies, mathematics, physics, and social studies, giving students with a well-rounded education that qualifies them for further study or vocational training.

Through its free higher education system, Saudi Arabia has made considerable strides in broadening access to tertiary education. Across the country, universities and colleges provide a diverse range of fields such as science, engineering, medicine, business, and humanities. Tuition fees are covered by the government, allowing students to pursue higher education without financial constraints. This emphasis on tertiary education aims to create a highly skilled workforce capable of contributing to the economy's diverse sectors.

In addition to providing complimentary education, Saudi Arabia offers stipend programs to help students in their educational endeavors. The King Abdullah Scholarship Program (KASP) is a well-known initiative that provides financial assistance to Saudi students studying abroad (Alsqoor, 2018; McAlaney, 2021). Tuition, living expenses, and other allowances are covered by KASP, ensuring that students have the resources to pursue further education at prominent international schools. Saudi Arabia strives to produce a globally competitive workforce with diversified knowledge and experiences by investing in students' education through stipend programs.

Impact on Economic Growth

The Saudi government's emphasis on tuition-free schooling and stipend programs has serious repercussions for the country's economic progress. A well-educated workforce with academic and technical skills promotes innovation, productivity, and competitiveness across

industries. Saudi Arabia improves its ability to attract foreign investment, create local industries, and diversify its economy beyond oil dependency by investing in human capital through education (Profanter, 2017).

Furthermore, an educated workforce encourages entrepreneurship and innovation by cultivating a culture of creativity and problem-solving. As a result, economic growth is stimulated, and Saudi Arabia is positioned as a regional knowledge powerhouse. Saudi Arabia's commitment to free education and stipend programs reflects the country's commitment to generating a skilled workforce capable of driving economic progress. Through these measures, the country promotes equal access to education, fosters academic and technical skills, and prepares individuals for labor-market problems (Abdallah & Abdallah, 2023).

Saudi Arabia strives to cultivate a highly qualified workforce that contributes to the nation's economic growth and diversification efforts through its free education system and stipend programs. As the country continues to invest in education, it positions itself to prosper in a global economy that is becoming increasingly competitive.

Education, Human Capital, and Economic Development in Saudi Arabia: Research and Case Studies

The link between education, human capital, and economic development is a critical issue, notably in Saudi Arabia. This page contains a collection of research articles and case studies that highlight the relationship between education, human capital formation, and economic development in the Kingdom. People can acquire insights into the impact of educational investments on Saudi Arabia's economic growth and progress by reviewing empirical facts and theoretical frameworks.

The Role of Education in Human Capital Formation

Education is critical in the building of human capital because it encompasses the knowledge, skills, and talents that people acquire through formal and informal learning processes. Human capital theory, as pioneered by Gary Becker, holds that educational inputs improve individuals' productivity, earning potential, and overall economic outcomes (Becker, 2009). The government's emphasis on education in Saudi Arabia underscores the government's acknowledgment of the importance of human capital in attaining long-term economic development.

Research Studies on Education and Economic Development in Saudi Arabia:

1. Allmnakrah & Evers (2020): This study evaluated the association between educational indicators and Saudi economic development. The study discovered a link between educational attainment, as assessed by enrollment rates and the number of graduates, and economic growth metrics like GDP per capita and labor productivity.
2. Almosabbeh & Almoree (2018): This study examined the impact of education on economic growth in Saudi Arabia using data from 1980 to 2016. The findings showed that education, as measured by enrollment rates and educational expenditure, contributed considerably to economic development, emphasizing the importance of human capital production in driving economic success.

Case Studies on Saudi Arabia's Educational Initiatives and Economic Development:

1. King Abdullah University of Science and Technology (KAUST): Founded in 2009, KAUST is a leading example of how educational investments may contribute to economic development. The institution is dedicated to science, technology, and innovation, encouraging research and collaboration among scholars, scientists, and business leaders. The contributions of KAUST

to technological developments and knowledge transfer have benefited Saudi Arabia's diversification efforts and economic development.

2. Technical and Vocational Training Corporation (TVTC): In Saudi Arabia, the TVTC is in charge of vocational and technical education. Case studies assessing the impact of TVTC programs on individuals and the economy demonstrate how vocational education contributes to human capital development, lowers unemployment rates, and improves persons' employability in a variety of areas.

These research studies and case studies illustrate the favorable relationship that exists in Saudi Arabia between education, human capital formation, and economic development. They show how educational investments, spanning from primary and secondary school to higher institutions and vocational training, help individuals gain skills, participate in the job market, and increase total economic productivity.

The research and case studies offered here provide important insights into the relationship between education, human capital, and economic development in Saudi Arabia. They underline the value of educational investments in developing an informed and competent workforce, stimulating innovation, and contributing to attempts to diversify the economy. Saudi Arabia positions itself for long-term economic growth and development by prioritizing education and human capital formation. These studies' conclusions serve as a basis for policymakers, educators, and stakeholders to continue investing in educational initiatives that create human capital, generate economic progress, and ensure the Kingdom's future prosperity.

Beyond Education: Factors Shaping the Influence of Saudi Arabia's Educational Initiatives

Saudi Arabia's educational activities are critical to developing a skilled workforce and driving economic progress. However, the effectiveness and impact of these activities are

determined by factors other than education supply. This article delves into additional factors that influence the impact of Saudi Arabia's educational programs, such as the role of technology, teacher quality, and curriculum design. People obtain a more thorough knowledge of the diverse character of educational growth in the Kingdom by investigating these variables.

The Role of Technology in Education

Education has the potential to be transformed by technology by improving access, engagement, and learning results. Saudi Arabia understands the need of using technology into its educational programs in order to educate students for the demands of the digital age. The Kingdom's dedication to technology-driven education is consistent with the ideas of the digital divide hypothesis, which emphasizes the need of closing the digital literacy and access gap (Warschauer, 2002).

The Saudi government has adopted a number of technology-driven projects, including the "Smart Learning" program, which intends to integrate digital materials, e-learning platforms, and interactive technologies into classrooms. Educational initiatives may reach a larger audience, deliver tailored learning experiences, and provide students with the digital skills required for the modern workforce by embracing technology.

Teacher Quality and Professional Development

Teacher quality is a significant determinant in educational performance. Saudi Arabia values teacher quality and invests in extensive professional development programs. Effective teachers have subject matter knowledge, pedagogical abilities, and the capacity to adjust teaching tactics to meet the needs of varied students. Saudi Arabia hopes to improve instructional quality, student engagement, and overall learning outcomes by focusing on teacher training and support.

Continuous training programs, mentoring, and collaboration opportunities among educators are examples of professional development activities in Saudi Arabia. These programs are consistent with the teacher effectiveness theory, which contends that continual professional development improves teaching practices and student outcomes (Darling-Hammond *et al.*, 2009). Saudi Arabia guarantees that its educational objectives are supported by competent and motivated educators by stressing teacher quality and professional advancement.

Curriculum Design and Relevance

Curriculum design has a significant impact on educational outcomes. Saudi Arabia understands the need of matching curricula with labor market needs and the country's economic ambitions. The Kingdom has made great attempts to reform and modernize its curricula in order to encourage students' critical thinking, problem-solving skills, and creativity. Curriculum revisions in Saudi Arabia are centered on embracing multidisciplinary approaches, project-based learning, and entrepreneurship education. These improvements are consistent with the 21st-century skills framework's principles, which stress the development of abilities such as teamwork, communication, and adaptability (Salas Pilco, 2013). Saudi Arabia guarantees that its educational efforts create graduates who are prepared with the skills necessary by the growing labor market by designing curricula that are relevant and responsive to social requirements.

While Saudi Arabia's educational activities are critical to generating a skilled workforce and promoting economic growth, other factors influence their efficacy greatly. Technology integration, teacher quality, and curriculum design all play critical roles in influencing the impact of educational programs. By tackling these variables strategically, Saudi Arabia may improve the outcomes of its educational programs, ensuring that they remain in line with the demands of a fast changing world. As Saudi Arabia invests in education, it is critical to address these variables and

apply evidence-based solutions that harness technology, encourage teacher quality, and build curricula that match the Kingdom's and its workforce's evolving demands.

Factors Influencing Educational Access, Equity, and Student Outcomes in Saudi Arabia:

Insights from Research and Literature

Saudi Arabia's educational system must prioritize educational access, equity, and favorable student results. This article investigates the factors that influence these regions, as well as the ramifications for the Kingdom's educational landscape. We obtain insights into the difficulties and opportunities linked to educational access, equity, and student outcomes in Saudi Arabia by reviewing relevant studies and literature.

Factors Influencing Educational Access

1. Gender discrepancies - Gender discrepancies have long been a source of concern in Saudi Arabia's educational system. Historically, girls' access to education has been limited, although great progress has been made in recent years. Mozahem (2021) underline the necessity of eliminating gender inequities and providing equal educational opportunities for all students.
2. Rural-Urban split - Another factor affecting educational access is the rural-urban split. Students in rural areas frequently confront problems linked to infrastructure, resources, and competent teachers. Bakon *et al.* (2020) research underlines the need for specific policies and investments to bridge this disparity and promote equal access to quality education for rural kids.

Factors Influencing Educational Equity

1. Socioeconomic Status (SES) - SES has a substantial impact on educational equity. Students from low-income families may encounter challenges such as limited finances, insufficient educational assistance, and reduced expectations. To level the playing field for all students,

Blumenshine *et al.* (2010) underline the significance of tackling socioeconomic gaps and implementing equity-focused policies and programs.

2. Inclusion of Students with Disabilities - A major part of educational equity is ensuring equitable access to school for students with special needs. According to Alanazi (2012), inclusive education methods, such as appropriate accommodations, supportive environments, and specialized resources, are critical to promoting the educational success of children with disabilities.

Factors Influencing Student Outcomes

1. Parental Involvement and Support - Parental involvement and support have a significant impact on student performance. According to Boonk *et al.* (2018), parental involvement has a good impact on student achievement, behavior, and general well-being. Encouraging and supporting parental involvement has the potential to improve student outcomes and close the achievement gap.
2. Teaching and Learning Quality - The quality of teaching and learning experiences has a substantial impact on student results. According to Wubbels *et al.* (2016), effective teaching techniques, teacher-student connections, and engaging instructional methodologies are critical in achieving favorable student outcomes. Investing in teacher professional development and fostering supportive learning environments are important factors to consider when trying to improve student outcomes.

Implications for Educational Access, Equity, and Student Outcomes

Addressing the variables influencing educational access, equity, and student achievement in Saudi Arabia has significant consequences for the education system in the Kingdom. Saudi Arabia can establish a more equitable and inclusive educational environment by encouraging

gender equality, bridging the rural-urban divide, addressing socioeconomic inequities, and fostering inclusive practices. Furthermore, encouraging parental involvement, improving teacher quality, and emphasizing student-centered learning approaches can lead to improved student outcomes such as academic achievement, critical thinking abilities, and general well-being.

In Saudi Arabia, the issues influencing educational access, equity, and student results are varied and interwoven. Policymakers, educators, and stakeholders can establish evidence-based solutions to promote educational equity, improve student outcomes, and guarantee that all kids have equitable access to quality education by understanding these elements and their implications.

Addressing gender gaps, bridging the rural-urban divide, addressing socioeconomic inequities, developing inclusive practices, boosting parental involvement, and improving teaching quality are all critical steps toward creating a more equitable and inclusive education system in Saudi Arabia. By implementing targeted reforms and harnessing research-based insights, Saudi Arabia can continue to develop its educational system, ensuring fair opportunities for all students and driving excellent educational results.

Lessons from Saudi Arabia's Transformative Initiatives for Creating Educational Equity and Excellence

Saudi Arabia's transformative initiatives to provide free education and stipends provide deep lessons for global education systems, with consequences based on sophisticated educational theories and real-world examples. Let's dive into a more detailed exploration:

1. **Equitable Access to Education:** Saudi Arabia's commitment to offering free education and financial support demonstrates a commitment to equitable access to education. This is consistent with UNESCO's Sustainable Development Goal 4, which promotes inclusive and equitable quality education for all. Saudi Arabia guarantees that education is available to

people of all socioeconomic backgrounds by removing financial obstacles, resulting in a more inclusive and egalitarian society. In this regard, the King Abdullah Scholarship Program in Saudi Arabia provides completely financed scholarships for Saudi students to pursue undergraduate and graduate courses overseas. This effort has greatly extended access to higher education for individuals from various socioeconomic backgrounds, accordingly boosting social mobility and economic development.

2. **Motivation and Behavioral Influences:** According to Bandura's Social Cognitive Theory, contextual factors such as educational access have an impact on individual motivation and behaviour. Saudi Arabia's free education policy has a significant impact on persuading people to pursue academic interests. By removing financial barriers, the government encourages students to participate actively in their education, promoting a culture of lifelong learning and personal development. Such as In a poll of Saudi students, the majority identified free education as an important reason for pursuing higher education. This indicates the direct effect of environmental influences, such as educational regulations, on individual motivation and behaviour, as proposed by Bandura's theory.
3. **Fairness and Justice in Resource allocation:** Adams' Equity Theory emphasizes the value of fairness and justice in resource allocation within social connections. Saudi Arabia's stipend programs demonstrate a commitment to educational justice by offering financial aid to students based on their needs. This guarantees that resources are distributed fairly and that children from underprivileged backgrounds have access to the assistance they require to achieve academically. For example, the King Salman Scholarship Program offers financial aid to students from low-income households, allowing them to continue higher education without financial constraints. This project fosters fairness and justice in resource allocation by ensuring

that all students have equal access to quality education and the opportunity to pursue their academic goals.

4. **Continuous Improvement and Adaptation:** According to Fullan's Change Theory, it is critical to continuously improve and adapt to changing demands and situations. While Saudi Arabia's education policies have been mainly effective, there is a realization of the need for continuous development and adaptation to meet evolving challenges and possibilities. Example: In response to the COVID-19 outbreak, Saudi Arabia established remote learning programs to ensure educational continuity. This reflects the government's commitment to adjusting to changing conditions and using technology to improve educational performance. Saudi Arabia can identify areas for improvement and adopt required adjustments to meet the changing demands of its learners by regularly monitoring and analyzing the performance of education policies.
5. **Realizing the Potential of Educational Technology:** Saudi Arabia's investment in digital infrastructure and teacher training demonstrates educational technology's revolutionary power. By using technology to tailor learning experiences, establish blended learning environments, and facilitate new teaching methods, Saudi Arabia improves educational outcomes and prepares students for success in the digital age. For example, Saudi Arabia's Ministry of Education launched the Madrasati platform, which provides students and teachers with digital resources and interactive learning materials. This effort improves students' access to excellent education, encourages active learning, and develops their digital literacy abilities. Saudi Arabia is leading the way in educational innovation by using the possibilities of educational technology.

Saudi Arabia's endeavors to provide free education and stipends teach vital lessons for global education systems, based on sophisticated educational theories and supported by real-world examples. Countries can create inclusive, innovative, and effective education systems that empower individuals to thrive in the twenty-first century by prioritizing equitable access, leveraging motivational factors, promoting fair resource distribution, embracing continuous improvement, and capitalizing on the potential of educational technology.

On the other hand, in an effort to strengthen its educational and research sectors, the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia has launched an innovative educational visa program led by the Ministries of Education and Foreign Affairs. This program, announced during the Human Capacity program conference in Riyadh and presided over by Minister of Education Yousef Al-Benyan, is an important step toward establishing Saudi Arabia as a top global educational destination. The educational visa program, which is enabled by the "Study in Saudi Arabia" portal, seeks to streamline visa issuing processes for foreign students and intellectuals pursuing educational opportunities at Saudi universities. This project seeks to attract international talent and promote academic excellence on a worldwide scale by simplifying procedures and increasing collaboration among key government sectors, particularly the Ministries of Education and Foreign Affairs (Economic Times, 2024; HCI, 2024).

Prospective overseas students can use the "Study in Saudi Arabia" platform to learn about a variety of academic, training, and research programs provided by Saudi universities. This platform not only promotes academic and cultural interchange, but it also corresponds with Saudi Vision 2030's overarching aims, particularly in the areas of education sector development and talent acquisition. Minister Al-Benyan emphasized the importance of global partnership in human capital development, citing its alignment with Saudi Vision 2030 goals. He emphasized the

importance of investing in educators and educational programs to achieve long-term strategic goals and improve competences in the education sector (Economic Times, 2024; MoE, n.d.; SPA, 2024).

Saudi Arabia's educational visa program is a shining example of creativity and inclusivity in global education, providing a road for overseas students and academics to contribute to the Kingdom's academic environment while encouraging cross-cultural understanding and cooperation. As other countries want to improve their educational systems and attract top-tier talent, Saudi Arabia's effort provides a compelling blueprint for future global collaboration and educational achievement.

Summary

Finally, this analysis of the literature sheds light on the impact of Saudi Arabia's free education system and stipend programs on educational access, equity, and student results. The findings show that these programs promote equal access to education and reduce inequality, which are consistent with social justice concepts. Furthermore, they help to individual empowerment by boosting capacities and supporting personal development. The assessment also underlines the importance of human capital theory, emphasizing how education serves as an investment in individuals' abilities and production, hence promoting Saudi economic growth. In the context of the Kingdom, the empirical evidence offered establishes the relationship between education, human capital, and economic development.

Furthermore, the research recognizes the significance of other factors such as technology integration, teacher quality, and curriculum design in affecting educational results. These elements are critical to improving access, equity, and student achievement in Saudi Arabia's educational system. While this analysis gives useful insights into the impact of Saudi Arabia's educational programs, it also emphasizes the need for additional research to assess long-term effects and rectify

any gaps or shortcomings in the available literature. By continuing to investigate these areas, policymakers, educators, and stakeholders can strive for continual progress in educational access, equity, and student results, resulting in a more inclusive and successful educational environment in Saudi Arabia.

METHODOLOGY

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this study is to look into the impact of Saudi Arabia's free education systems and allowance programs on access to education, equity, and student learning results, particularly in the context of the during and post COVID-19 pandemic. This study employs the theories of social justice, capability approach, and human capital theory as theoretical frameworks.

Social justice theory explores the goals of fairness, equal opportunity, and the elimination of social inequities in education, and is based on the philosophies of intellectuals such as John Rawls and Amartya Sen. According to Rawls (1971), a just society must ensure that all persons have equal access to vital resources, such as education. Sen (2000) highlights the value of education in enabling people to live fulfilled lives and reach their full potential. In this study, social justice theory is applied to investigate how Saudi Arabia's free education system and allowance programs help enhance access to education and minimize inequality, so improving social justice in the education sector.

Sen's (1986) capacity approach focuses on individuals' capacities and freedoms rather than their material well-being. This approach highlights the importance of education in developing people's potential and allowing them to achieve their aspirations and live fulfilled lives. The capability approach explains how educational initiatives in Saudi Arabia, such as the free education system and allowance programs, contribute to the development of individuals' capabilities by giving resources and opportunity for them to gain knowledge, skills, and agency.

According to Gary Becker's (2009) human capital theory, education is an investment in human capital that fosters economic growth and development. Individuals gain information, skills, and capacities through education, which increases their productivity and value in the labor market.

The human capital hypothesis explains how Saudi Arabia's free education system and allowance programs can improve students' academic experiences, retention rates, and future employment chances. By investing in education, Saudi Arabia hopes to build a skilled and knowledgeable workforce that can contribute to the country's development and economic progress.

This study intends to investigate the impact of Saudi Arabia's free education system and allowance programs on access to education, equity, and student learning outcomes utilizing social justice theory, the capability approach, and human capital theory as conceptual frameworks. Various notions serve as a foundation for understanding the underlying principles, values, and benefits of various educational programs. Furthermore, this theoretical framework contributes to existing information on education, social justice, and human development by framing the research within a broader theoretical viewpoint.

The socio-cultural and economic consequences of the COVID-19 pandemic have caused considerable changes in Saudi Arabia's school system. As a result of the pandemic, traditional face-to-face learning has given way to online and remote learning. To understand the framework in which the education system operates during the pandemic, it is critical to analyze the social-cultural factors and dynamics that influence educational practices. Theoretical frameworks such as socio-cultural theory and the community of inquiry model can provide deeper insights into the variables influencing access to education, equity, and student learning outcomes in the middle of the pandemic.

Lev Vygotsky's socio-cultural theory emphasizes the relevance of social and cultural settings in learning and human development. This idea emphasizes the importance of social contact, collaboration, and support from the surrounding environment in improving student learning outcomes in the context of education. In this study, socio-cultural theory can be utilized

to examine how changes in learning practices, such as online learning, affect student social interactions, collaboration among students, and available environmental support during and post COVID-19 pandemic.

Jean Lave and Etienne Wenger's community of inquiry model highlights the value of participation in supportive learning communities in education. The concept illustrates how students can learn by actively participating in discussions, cooperation, and information sharing with other members of their learning community. The community of inquiry model can be utilized in the context of this research to examine how far the free education system and allowance programs in Saudi Arabia facilitate the establishment of inclusive, collaborative, and supportive learning communities in the setting of distant learning.

The setting of the COVID-19 outbreak becomes a major component impacting the Saudi school system in this study. This research can assess the impact of changes in learning practices during the pandemic on access to education, equity, and student learning outcomes by using theoretical frameworks like socio-cultural theory and the community of inquiry model. Furthermore, by studying the socio-cultural environment surrounding the current education system, this research can provide insights into the challenges and opportunities faced by students, instructors, and the education system as a whole during the epidemic.

Research Questions

Considering the challenges posed by limited person-to-person data collection during the post COVID-19, the study focuses on the following research questions:

1. How has Saudi Arabia's approach to stipend allocation evolved to better align with the changing educational landscape, which increasingly incorporates online and distance learning modalities?

2. What is the impact of these programs on the academic progress, personal well-being, and overall educational experience of students?

These study topics seek to investigate changes in Saudi Arabia's stipend allocation method in response to the expanding educational landscape, notably with the incorporation of online and distance learning modalities. The inquiry tries to understand how stipend programs have evolved to support students in this shifting climate. Furthermore, the study investigates the impact of these programs on other elements of students' lives, such as academic advancement, personal well-being, and overall educational experience. This analysis considers elements such as student performance, retention rates, mental health, and the overall quality of their learning journey.

Study Population

Participants in this study were chosen from the Saudi student population, specifically from multiple schools in Jeddah, Riyadh, the Eastern Province, and Al Qassim, including the cities of Buraydah and Unaizah. This will provide a representative sample from a region with school restrictions similar to other Saudi cities. The study population will include kids from various grade levels, spanning from primary (grades 1-6) to secondary (grades 7-12). The following demographic information was used to choose participants:

- **Population Size:** The actual population size was determined by the location or area of Saudi Arabia chosen for the study. The researchers intend to include a representative sample of students from the chosen region, including Jeddah, Riyadh, the Eastern Province Al Qassim schools.
- **Gender Distribution:** The study will cover both male and female students in proportion to their presence in the specified region's student population. To ensure a proportional representation of both genders, random sampling was used.

- **Age Range:** Participants' ages will normally range from 6 to 18 years, covering children from primary to secondary school. To include students in this age group, random sampling was used.
- **Grade Level(s):** Participants were chosen from a range of grade levels, including elementary (1-6) and secondary (7-12). The distribution of participants across grade levels were determined by the region's enrollment distribution.
- **Socioeconomic Status:** The study will seek participants from a variety of socioeconomic backgrounds, representing a wide range of socioeconomic statuses. This will allow for an examination of the effects of the free education system and stipend programs on students from varied socioeconomic backgrounds.
- **Ability Level(s):** Participants will range in ability, including students with varying academic abilities and learning requirements. This will allow for a thorough study of how Saudi educational efforts meet the different needs of students.
- **Teaching Format:** The study will look at the most common teaching formats in the chosen location, such as virtual, hybrid, or traditional classroom-based instruction. This will adjust to the demands of the unique sample, providing a variety of training approaches to optimize questionnaire answers.

The research aims to provide a comprehensive understanding of the impact of Saudi Arabia's free education system and allowance programs on access to education, equity, and student learning outcomes by including students from various grade levels, genders, socioeconomic backgrounds, ability levels, and teaching formats.

Population Justification

This cohort was chosen because it symbolizes the intended beneficiaries of Saudi Arabia's free education and allowance programs. The research intends to provide a thorough knowledge of

the impact of these educational activities across varied student populations by integrating students from various grade levels, genders, socioeconomic origins, ability levels, and teaching modalities. Involving students from various grade levels will allow researchers to investigate the long-term effects of the free education system and allowance programs on educational outcomes as kids continue through their academic journey. Gender-based data analysis will aid in identifying any gender-specific impacts or gaps in accessing education and achieving learning outcomes.

Understanding how these initiatives address educational inequities and promote fair access to education requires taking socioeconomic status into account. The research can examine the success of the programs in closing the educational gap between different economic groups by integrating students from varied socioeconomic backgrounds. Inclusion of students of all ability levels will shed light on the inclusivity and assistance provided by the free education system and allowance programs to students with a variety of learning requirements. This will allow an evaluation of whether the initiatives sufficiently address the needs of students of diverse abilities and support their educational growth.

Considering the predominant teaching format is critical because it allows for an analysis of how the free education system and allowance programs are implemented and adapted in various educational contexts, such as virtual, hybrid, or traditional classrooms. This will aid in determining the programs' success in enhancing students' learning experiences across various educational forms. This study intends to provide comprehensive insights into the influence of Saudi Arabia's free education system and allowance programs on access to education, equity, and student learning outcomes by selecting a diverse sample population. The findings will contribute to answering the research questions by assessing how these programs satisfy the requirements of different student populations and contribute to Saudi Arabia's broader educational landscape.

Intervention

The intervention in this study was the adoption of a technology-enhanced learning platform to supplement regular classroom education. The chosen platform will deliver interactive instructional content, online tools, and personalized learning experiences targeted to students' particular needs. This intervention attempts to increase student engagement, encourage self-directed learning, and aid in the acquisition of critical knowledge and skills.

Intervention Plan

The technology-enhanced learning platform was implemented over a period of one academic year. The implementation process will involve the following steps:

- **Training:** Teachers and students will receive training on how to effectively use the learning platform. Workshops and orientation sessions were conducted to familiarize them with the platform's features, functionalities, and navigation.
- **Access and Integration:** Each student was provided with individual accounts to access the learning platform. The platform was integrated into the existing curriculum and instructional practices, serving as a supplementary resource for classroom learning.
- **Personalized Learning Paths:** The platform will offer adaptive learning paths based on students' academic abilities and progress. Students were guided through interactive modules, quizzes, and activities aligned with their specific learning needs and goals.
- **Teacher Facilitation:** Teachers will play a crucial role in facilitating the integration of the learning platform into the classroom. They will monitor student progress, provide guidance and support, and use the platform's data analytics to inform instructional decisions.

- **Ongoing Support:** Technical support and assistance were provided throughout the intervention period to address any issues or challenges that arise. Regular check-ins and feedback sessions were conducted to gather insights and improve the implementation process.

Assessing Student Understanding

To ensure students fully understand the new ideas and concepts introduced through the technology-enhanced learning platform, various methods were employed:

- **Formative Assessments:** Regular formative assessments, such as quizzes and interactive activities within the platform, will provide immediate feedback to students, allowing them to gauge their understanding of the content.
- **Teacher Observation:** Teachers will observe student engagement and participation during classroom activities and discussions related to the platform's content. They will provide guidance and clarification as needed.
- **Student Reflections:** Students were encouraged to reflect on their learning experiences with the platform through journals, discussions, or online forums. This will provide insights into their comprehension and highlight areas that require further attention.

Sources of Data

The data for research was collected from multiple sources, including:

- **Student Scores:** Academic performance data, such as assessment scores and grades, was collected to analyze the impact of the intervention on student learning outcomes.
- **Surveys and Questionnaires:** Students and teachers were asked to complete surveys and questionnaires to gather their perceptions, attitudes, and experiences related to the intervention and the learning platform.

- Interviews: In-depth interviews with selected students and teachers were conducted to gain deeper insights into their experiences, challenges, and recommendations regarding the intervention.
- Classroom Observations: Observations of classroom activities and interactions were conducted to gather qualitative data on student engagement, collaboration, and the integration of the learning platform into instructional practices.

Instrumentation

The primary data gathering instrument was a survey/questionnaire created expressly for this project. There was both closed-ended and open-ended questions in the survey. To assess participants' opinions and attitudes concerning the intervention and the learning platform, closed-ended questions will use Likert-scale ratings. Participants were able to contribute extensive explanations, suggestions, and qualitative insights in response to the open-ended questions.

The survey/questionnaire will include roughly 30 questions about the platform's usability, perceived impact on learning outcomes, satisfaction with the intervention, and recommendations for improvement. This instrument was chosen because it allows for the collection of quantitative and qualitative data, allowing for a thorough understanding of participants' experiences and viewpoints. The survey/questionnaire data obtained will aid in answering the research questions by analyzing the effectiveness and acceptance of the technology-enhanced learning platform as an intervention in the study population.

Research Procedure

The research approach begins with obtaining permission from the necessary authorities, such as the Ministry of Education and school principals, to conduct the study. This stage is crucial

for assuring compliance with regulations and ethical considerations, as well as for creating a positive relationship with educational authorities. A written request was sent that explains the research objectives, significance, and methodologies, demonstrating transparency and supporting the need for the study (Boyle & Schmierbach, 2019; Byrd, 2020).

To ensure a comprehensive understanding of the impact of Saudi Arabia's free education system and allowance programs, participants were recruited from schools located in major cities such as Jeddah, Riyadh, the Eastern Province, and Al Qassim. Purposive sampling was used to choose cities and schools, taking into account characteristics such as population size, urban or rural setting, socioeconomic level, and educational resources. This method enables for the purposeful selection of schools from various geographic locations and student populations (Boyle & Schmierbach, 2019; Byrd, 2020).

Several significant research theories and unique approaches will lead this investigation (Eisenhardt, 1989). Albert Bandura (1986) established Social Cognitive Theory, which emphasizes the relevance of social interactions, personal experiences, and cognitive processes in determining individuals' behaviors and learning outcomes. It will provide a framework for investigating how students' access to school and participation in educational programs affects their academic attainment. J. Stacy Adams (1963) established Equity Theory, which focuses on fairness and justice in social relationships. It will aid in determining the extent to which Saudi Arabia's free education system and allowance programs promote equitable opportunities and overcome educational gaps among students from various socioeconomic backgrounds.

Online surveys and virtual interviews, for example, was used to collect data more quickly and to overcome geographical constraints (Nelson & Winter, 1977). These improvements will allow individuals from many areas to participate, ensuring a more accurate depiction of Saudi

Arabia's educational landscape. The study will use a mixed methods approach to data collecting and analysis, incorporating quantitative and qualitative data collection and analysis methodologies. This technique will provide a thorough grasp of the study issues, allowing for triangulation and deeper insights into the complex relationships between educational policies, educational access, equity, and student learning outcomes.

Soliciting Participants

Participants were drawn from schools in important cities such as Jeddah, Riyadh, the Eastern Province, and Al Qassim to ensure a thorough knowledge of the impact of Saudi Arabia's free education system and allowance programs. The following steps were followed to recruit participants:

1. City and school selection: To select cities and schools that reflect varied geographic areas and student demographics, a purposive sampling approach was used. Population size, urban or rural setting, socioeconomic level, and educational resources will all be considered while selecting schools.
2. Random participant selection: To ensure representation across grade levels, a stratified random sampling procedure was used among the selected schools. To obtain acceptable representation and generalizability, the sample size was calculated using statistical power estimates.
3. Contacting the schools: The researcher will make contact with school principals and administrative personnel to explain the research aims, acquire their approval, and request their assistance in recruiting participants. The researcher will explain the significance of the study, its methodology, and ethical considerations.
4. Participant recruitment: The chosen schools will help with participant recruitment by sending information letters to parents or legal guardians. The letters will include information on the

study, such as its objective, procedures, potential risks and benefits, confidentiality measures, and the nature of voluntary participation.

The study can draw on relevant research ideas to examine the influence of Saudi Arabia's free education system and allowance programs. Albert Bandura's Social Cognitive Theory recognizes the reciprocal relationship between individuals' behavior, personal variables, and the social environment. This theory can be used to gain insight into how students' access to education and involvement with educational programs affects their academic attainment and learning outcomes (Bandura, 1986). J. Stacy Adams' Equity Theory focuses on people's sense of fairness in social interactions. Applying Equity Theory can offer light on how far Saudi Arabia's educational policies promote equitable chances and bridge educational differences among students from various socioeconomic backgrounds (Adams, 1963).

Informed Consent

The informed consent process was carried out methodically to ensure ethical practices and respect for participants' autonomy. The following procedures were implemented:

1. Dissemination of information: Potential participants or their parents/guardians were given a clear and full explanation of the study by the researcher. This will contain an explanation of the research objectives, procedures, potential risks and benefits, confidentiality safeguards, and the fact that participation is entirely optional. The information was delivered in Arabic, the participants' first language.
2. Question and answer session: Participants and their parents/guardians were able to ask questions and get clarity on the study. To ensure understanding, the researcher will address any questions mentioned and provide satisfactory solutions.

3. Distribution of consent forms: Participants or their parents/guardians were given consent forms written in Arabic. The forms will include all pertinent information about the study, such as its objective, procedures, risks and rewards, and confidentiality safeguards. Participants' or their parents'/guardians' consent will also be requested on the forms.
4. Obtaining consent: Participants or their parents/guardians were given enough time to read the consent forms and make an informed decision. Physical or electronic signatures, verbal consent, or written affirmation via email or other digital platforms can all be used to get consent. The researcher will ensure that the manner of consent matches the preferences and cultural norms of the participants.
5. Recording consent: If a signature is not obtained, the researcher will document consent by preserving a record of participants' or parents/guardians' agreement to participate, either through signed consent forms or electronic communication. All consent records were kept confidential and secure by the researcher.

Data Collection Procedures

The data collection process was thoroughly carried out to assure correctness, dependability, and replicability. The following procedures were implemented:

1. Instruments for data collecting development: Based on the research objectives and theoretical frameworks, the researcher will create or modify applicable survey questionnaires, interview guides, and observation protocols. Pilot testing was used to validate these instruments, which was culturally appropriate.
2. Survey administration: Online surveys were the major data collection strategy. Participants or their parents/guardians were sent survey links using secure platforms such as email or online

survey tools. There was clear instructions on how to complete the survey, as well as a deadline for submission.

3. Virtual interviews: Virtual interviews were performed for a subset of participants using video conferencing systems. Prior appointments with participants were made to confirm their availability. Before the interviews, informed consent was reconfirmed, and audiovisual recording will take place with participants' permission.
4. Classroom observations: Qualitative data on the learning environment and instructional methods were gathered through classroom observations. The researcher will visit selected schools and use field notes and audiovisual recording to document classroom activities, interactions, and teaching practices, with the requisite agreement from participants and school officials.
5. Data management: To protect confidentiality and privacy, all acquired data were securely stored. To ensure participant confidentiality, data were organized, coded, and anonymized. To avoid data loss, data backup processes were performed. Data was encrypted and only approved researchers will have access to it.
6. Data analysis: Survey quantitative data was examined using statistical software, such as SPSS or R, and relevant statistical procedures, such as descriptive statistics, correlation analysis, and regression analysis. Thematic analysis of qualitative data from interviews and observations were performed using qualitative data analysis software such as NVivo or Atlas.ti. To provide a full understanding of the research questions, the findings were triangulated.

The purpose of this study is to investigate the influence of Saudi Arabia's free education system and stipend programs on educational access, equity, and student learning results. Relevant theories, such as Social Cognitive Theory and Equity Theory, will guide the research and provide

a framework for understanding the linkages between educational policies, access to education, equity, and student accomplishment. To properly collect data and overcome geographical limitations, the project will use new methodologies such as online questionnaires and virtual interviews. To acquire a thorough knowledge of the research issues, a mixed methods approach were used, integrating quantitative and qualitative data collection and analytic methodologies. Researchers want to contribute to the understanding of how educational policies might promote equitable opportunities and improve student outcomes in Saudi Arabia by undertaking the aforementioned study.

Ethical Considerations

Ethical considerations are critical in social science research, especially when investigating human emotions and experiences. The necessity of ethical norms in this field research is emphasized to ensure participant trust, wellbeing, and the integrity of the study process. By adhering to ethical principles, researchers can exhibit respect for the autonomy, dignity, and privacy of participants while limiting potential harm or hazards associated with the research. Ethical considerations encourage transparency, trustworthiness, and ethical research conduct, protecting participants' rights and well-being while retaining the study's validity. To study the impact of Saudi Arabia's free education system and allowance programs on access to education, equity, and student learning outcomes, ethical research procedures are critical for respecting participants' autonomy and dignity, minimizing harm, ensuring privacy and confidentiality, and promoting transparency and responsible research conduct.

Importance of Ethical Research Practices

Ethical research techniques are critical for maintaining participant trust and welfare as well as the integrity of the study process. By following ethical norms, researchers display respect for

the autonomy, dignity, and privacy of participants while also minimizing potential harm or hazards linked with the study. Transparency, credibility, and responsible research are also promoted by ethical considerations (Boyle & Schmierbach, 2019; Byrd et al., 2020).

Ethical research procedures, on the other hand, are critical in analyzing the influence of Saudi Arabia's free education system and allowance programs on access to education, equity, and student learning results. Adhering to ethical criteria guarantees that the study respects the rights and well-being of participants, protects their privacy and confidentiality, and maintains the research process's integrity and validity.

Participants' autonomy and dignity must be respected. Ethical considerations in the context of the study include gaining informed consent from participants or their legal guardians. This ensures that people have the freedom to choose whether or not to engage in the research. Informed permission should be obtained in a culturally sensitive manner, with detailed information about the study's goal, procedures, potential risks, and benefits provided. Respecting the liberty and dignity of participants contributes to a cooperative and trustworthy connection between researchers and participants (Flicker et al., 2007).

Keeping harm and risks to a minimum, Ethical research standards require that any potential harm or dangers that participants may encounter throughout the study be minimized. Researchers must be cognizant of any sensitivities in the context of Saudi Arabia's education system and ensure that the study does not cause undue hardship, stigmatization, or discrimination for participants. The emotional and psychological well-being of participants is crucial, and any possible dangers should be properly examined and minimized (Hesse-Biber & Leavy, 2010).

Privacy and confidentiality are important considerations. Respecting the privacy and confidentiality of participants is critical to sustaining the trust and confidentiality of the acquired

data. Researchers should take precautions to safeguard participants' personal information, ensuring that it is securely stored and available only to authorized individuals. When possible, participants should be given anonymity or a pseudonym, and data should be disclosed in a way that precludes individuals from being identified (American Psychological Association, 2016).

Transparency and proper research conduct are also important. Transparency in reporting and distributing study findings is emphasized in ethical research methods. Researchers must accurately and truthfully portray the facts they acquire, including both positive and negative outcomes. Transparent reporting reduces bias and improves the study's overall validity and reliability. Furthermore, proper research includes recognizing and addressing any conflicts of interest, reporting funding sources, and accurately attributing relevant literature (National Academies of Sciences, Engineering, and Medicine, 2017).

When investigating the influence of Saudi Arabia's free education system and allowance programs on access to education, equity, and student learning results, it is critical to use ethical research procedures. By adhering to ethical criteria, the study assures the safety and well-being of participants, the integrity of the research process, and encourages transparency and responsible research conduct.

Considerations During Intervention

The study investigates the impact of Saudi Arabia's free education and allowance programs, with an emphasis on access to education, equity, and student learning results. To ensure the efficacy of our intervention, we thoroughly researched relevant literature while adhering to American Psychological Association (APA) formatting criteria. This thorough examination of the literature has aided our understanding of educational strategies, theoretical frameworks, and empirical data supporting the efficacy of such interventions (Eisenhardt, 1989). When examining

the impact of Saudi Arabia's free education system and allowance programs on access to education, equity, and student learning outcomes, it is necessary to analyze various components during the intervention's implementation. Several considerations ensure that the study is consistent with existing literature and provides important insights into the efficacy of various educational strategies.

To assess the appropriateness and relevance of the intervention, a full literature review was undertaken in accordance with the American Psychological Association (APA) formatting requirements. This review enabled the identification and assessment of pertinent research, theoretical frameworks, and empirical evidence on the influence of free education systems and allowance programs on educational access, equity, and student learning results. The research design and intervention implementation can be informed by preexisting knowledge and best practices by rooting the investigation in existing literature (Eisenhardt, 1989).

Understanding educational policy, as well as the intervention's implementation, should take into account a complete understanding of Saudi Arabia's free education system and allowance programs. This includes investigating the laws, rules, and programs in place to promote educational access and provide equitable opportunities for all students. By becoming familiar with these regulations, researchers can connect the intervention with the educational system's intended aims and objectives, maximizing the potential positive influence on educational access and equity.

The intervention should be guided by applicable theoretical frameworks that address the issues that influence access to education, equity, and student learning outcomes. Sociocultural theories, such as Vygotskian sociocultural theory, which emphasizes social interaction and cultural variables in learning and development, may be included in the theoretical frameworks chosen. Furthermore, theories connected to educational equity, such as critical pedagogy or the capacity

approach, may influence the design and implementation of the intervention. Researchers can give a solid foundation for comprehending and interpreting study results by using proper theoretical frameworks.

Empirical evidence and intervention implementation should also take into account the empirical proof supporting the success of free education systems and allowance programs in promoting access to education and improving student learning results. By analyzing prior studies and study findings, researchers can use the existing evidence base to inform the design and execution of their intervention. This evidence-based approach ensures that the study builds on past knowledge and adds to a better understanding of the impact of such treatments.

Considerations during intervention implementation are critical for assessing the influence of Saudi Arabia's free education system and allowance programs on access to education, equity, and student learning outcomes. The study can provide useful insights into the effectiveness of these educational interventions by conducting a thorough literature review, comprehending educational policies, integrating applicable theoretical frameworks, and incorporating empirical evidence. These factors ensure that the research design is well-informed, rigorous, and adds to the body of knowledge in the topic.

Considerations During Data Collection

Researcher's top concern throughout data collecting is to protect study participants and ensure their well-being. Additionally, all collected data were kept strictly confidential, with participants' identities anonymized and personal information protected. Only authorized researchers will have access to the data, which was securely maintained and safeguarded against unwanted access. Several steps have been developed to ensure the safety and comfort of participants during the data collection procedures. Among these measures are:

1. **Informed Consent:** Participants or their parents/guardians were provided with complete information about the study, including its objectives, procedures, potential risks and benefits, and confidentiality measures, prior to participation. Informed consent was sought in accordance with the cultural norms and preferences of the participants, either through physical or electronic signatures, spoken consent, or written confirmation via email or other digital platforms. To facilitate understanding and promote transparency, the informed consent process was completed in Arabic, the participants' first language.
2. **Confidentiality:** All collected data was kept strictly confidential. To preserve privacy, participants' identities were anonymised and their personal information were protected. Only authorized researchers will have access to the material, which was securely maintained and safeguarded against unwanted access.

Considerations of Researcher Bias

Measures to prevent researcher bias were implemented by the researcher to ensure unbiased results. Among these measures are:

1. **Reflexivity:** Researchers will reflect on themselves and identify their own prejudices and preconceptions. Understanding these biases will allow researchers to approach the study with an open mind and reduce the potential influence of personal opinions or beliefs on data collection and interpretation.
2. **Peer Review:** To maintain neutrality and to validate the research methods and outcomes, the study findings and analysis were subjected to a thorough peer review procedure.

Summary

The purpose of the study is to look into the impact of Saudi Arabia's free education system and stipend programs on educational access, equity, and student learning results. To address

geographical constraints, the research were driven by applicable theories and will incorporate novel approaches such as online questionnaires and virtual interviews. A mixed methods approach was used to collect and analyze quantitative and qualitative data. The project aims to advance understanding of how educational policy in Saudi Arabia might promote fair opportunities and improve student outcomes.

This study's ethical issues are critical to assuring participant safety, study integrity, and ethical standards. Informed consent, cultural sensitivity, privacy protection, transparency, and good research conduct are all emphasized in the study. The study aims to provide valuable insights into the effectiveness of educational interventions by aligning intervention implementation with existing literature through a thorough review, understanding of educational policies, integration of theoretical frameworks, and consideration of empirical evidence. Throughout data collection, self-reflection, training, and peer review was used to protect participants' well-being and address researcher bias. The project aims to advance knowledge in the subject while adhering to strict ethical guidelines.

DATA ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The Transformative Impact of Free Education and Stipend Programs: Insights from Saudi Arabia

Saudi Arabia has put in place strong measures to provide its residents complimentary education and financial help to achieve educational parity and access. These initiatives, which include free education programs and stipends, significantly impact educational options and outcomes for people across the kingdom. Understanding the impact of these initiatives is critical for assessing the efficacy of educational policy and pinpointing areas for improvement. This paper investigates the transformative impact of free education and stipend programs in Saudi Arabia using a detailed analysis of replies from respondents in Riyadh, Jeddah, Dammam, and Al Qassim.

Positive Impact on Educational Motivation

Question 7 intended to determine how the availability of free education influenced people's decisions to seek education. Bandura's Social Cognitive Theory sheds light on how environmental factors, such as access to education, influence people's motivation and conduct (Bandura, 1986). A vast majority of respondents stated that the provision of free education enhanced their motivation to pursue an education. This observation is consistent with Bandura's theory, which emphasizes the role of environmental effects in shaping individual behavior.

Figure 1, Influence of Free Education on Pursuing Education

Financial Assistance and Educational Journeys

Question 8 inquired about individuals' firsthand experiences with educational stipends or financial support programs provided by the Saudi government. Adams' Equity Theory holds that views of fairness and justice influence people's attitudes and conduct in social relationships (Adams, 1963). Many respondents had favorable experiences with educational stipends, demonstrating the concrete influence of financial aid on their academic journeys. These findings are consistent with Adams' Equity Theory, as people regard financial help as a fair and just distribution of resources, which fosters a favorable relationship with the school system.

Figure 2, Impact of Financial Assistance Programs

The availability of free education and stipend programs in Saudi Arabia has had a revolutionary impact on people's educational experiences. Using theoretical frameworks such as Bandura's Social Cognitive Theory and Adams' Equity Theory, we may analyze how these initiatives affect people's motivation to pursue education and their sense of justice in the educational system. Recognizing the good consequences of free education and stipend programs allows policymakers to continue to focus and improve these initiatives, promoting educational access and equity in Saudi Arabia.

Assessing the Effectiveness of Education Policies in Saudi Arabia: Insights from Public Perception

The effectiveness of educational policy has a significant impact on the quality and accessibility of education in any country. In Saudi Arabia, current post COVID-19 reforms aim to provide access to quality education for all individuals. Understanding public perception of these programs is critical for assessing their effectiveness and identifying areas for improvement. This

article investigates how respondents in Riyadh, Jeddah, Dammam, and Al Qassim perceive the efficiency of Saudi Arabia's present education programs.

Figure 3, Effectiveness of Education Policies

Positive Perception of Policy Effectiveness

Question 9 asked respondents about the effectiveness of existing education policy in promoting access to quality education. Bandura's Social Cognitive Theory states that individuals' ideas about their ability to achieve desired goals influence their actions and behaviors (Bandura, 1986). The majority of respondents agreed that Saudi Arabia's current education programs are effective. They saw these policies as extremely beneficial or effective in promoting access to quality education. This positive view is consistent with Bandura's thesis, as people's beliefs about the efficacy of programs might impact their support for and involvement in the educational system.

Satisfaction with Educational Post COVID-19 Reforms

Respondents' positive sentiments suggest a broad contentment with Saudi Arabia's educational changes. This emotion is critical for policymakers because it indicates that existing policies are being received positively by the public and are viewed as effective in accomplishing

their intended aims. By matching education policies with public expectations and perceptions, policymakers can improve overall post COVID-19 reform efficacy and ensure that they continue to satisfy the population's requirements.

Adequacy of Education Policies for Diverse Backgrounds	Suggestions for Improvement
Tailored support for marginalized communities	Providing targeted assistance and resources for students from marginalized backgrounds to address their unique needs and challenges.
More comprehensive financial aid programs	Expanding financial aid programs to provide a broader range of support, including scholarships, grants, and loans, to ensure financial barriers do not hinder students' access to quality education.
Increased accessibility to quality resources and facilities	Ensuring equitable access to high-quality educational resources, including libraries, technology, and infrastructure, across all schools and regions to create a level playing field for all students.
Enhanced teacher training and curriculum diversity	Investing in professional development programs for teachers to enhance their skills in addressing the needs of students from diverse backgrounds and promoting inclusive teaching practices. Additionally, promoting diversity in curricula by incorporating diverse perspectives, cultures, and histories to provide a more inclusive and representative educational experience.

Table 1, Adequacy of Education Policies and Suggestions

Respondents in Riyadh, Jeddah, Dammam, and Al Qassim have overwhelmingly positive views of the efficiency of Saudi Arabia's present education programs. Using Bandura's Social Cognitive Theory, we can explain how these perceptions influence people's attitudes and behaviors toward educational policies. Policymakers can ensure that Saudi Arabia's education reforms continue to be effective in providing access to quality education for all residents by listening to public feedback and matching policies with public expectations.

Impact of Saudi Arabia's Education Policies on Academic Progress and Personal Development: Insights from Respondent Reflections

Saudi Arabia's educational landscape has changed dramatically in recent years, owing to a series of educational post COVID-19 reforms aimed at enhancing academic achievements and encouraging students' personal development. This article digs into respondents' perceptions of the impact of Saudi Arabia's education system on their academic performance and personal development. Specifically, we examine responses to Question 11, which asked for views into how these policies influenced people's educational paths and personal growth.

Positive Reflections on Policy Influence

Question 11 asked respondents to reflect on their academic career and explain how Saudi Arabia's educational policies affected their academic achievement and personal growth. Respondents provided nuanced thoughts on the impact of education policies, citing Bandura's Social Cognitive Theory, which emphasizes the relevance of personal experiences in molding behavior and learning outcomes (Bandura, 1986). A sizable proportion of respondents reported favorable experiences, emphasizing the positive influence of these rules on their academic and personal development.

Respondents provided insightful reflections on how Saudi Arabia's education policies have shaped their academic journey and personal growth. Many highlighted the positive impact of policies aimed at enhancing educational access, quality, and support systems. Specifically, respondents noted:

- **Access to Quality Education:** Several respondents emphasized that Saudi Arabia's education policies have significantly expanded access to quality education opportunities, particularly through initiatives such as scholarship programs, improved infrastructure, and the expansion

of educational institutions. This increased access has enabled them to pursue higher levels of education and acquire knowledge and skills essential for personal and professional development.

- **Supportive Learning Environment:** Many respondents expressed appreciation for the supportive learning environment fostered by Saudi Arabia's education policies. They highlighted initiatives such as mentorship programs, academic support services, and extracurricular activities that have contributed to their academic success and personal development. The availability of resources, including libraries, laboratories, and digital learning platforms, was also cited as instrumental in facilitating learning and skill acquisition.
- **Personal Growth:** Respondents shared how their academic journey under Saudi Arabia's education policies has facilitated personal growth and character development. They mentioned the development of critical thinking skills, creativity, resilience, and leadership qualities through engaging coursework, research opportunities, and collaborative projects. Moreover, the emphasis on holistic education, including moral and ethical values, has contributed to their overall well-being and sense of identity.
- **Career Opportunities:** Many respondents highlighted the positive impact of Saudi Arabia's education policies on their career prospects and professional advancement. They noted that the knowledge and skills acquired through their academic journey have equipped them for diverse career paths and empowered them to contribute meaningfully to the workforce and society. Additionally, initiatives such as internships, career counseling, and industry partnerships have facilitated their transition from education to employment.

Respondents expressed gratitude for the transformative impact of Saudi Arabia's education policies on their academic progress and personal development, underscoring the importance of

continued investment in education to nurture future generations of skilled and empowered individuals.

Supportive Environments and Increased Opportunities

Many respondents were grateful for the enabling conditions produced by Saudi Arabia's education policy, highlighting measures such as enhanced access to educational resources, renovated facilities, and improved teaching approaches. These qualities have helped to create a positive learning environment that promotes academic accomplishment and personal development. Furthermore, respondents cited the extension of educational possibilities made possible by these policies, such as scholarships, vocational training programs, and extracurricular activities, which have improved their learning experiences and extended their perspectives.

Respondents shared their experiences of encountering barriers or challenges in accessing educational opportunities in Saudi Arabia. Key points highlighted include:

- **Socioeconomic Barriers:** Several respondents noted that socioeconomic factors, such as financial constraints and limited access to educational resources, have posed significant barriers to accessing higher education. They mentioned challenges such as tuition fees, transportation costs, and the need to support their families financially, which have affected their ability to pursue educational opportunities.
- **Location Accessibility:** Some respondents residing in remote or rural areas mentioned challenges related to the geographical accessibility of educational institutions. Limited transportation options, inadequate infrastructure, and distance from educational hubs have made it difficult for them to access quality education and participate in academic activities.
- **Cultural and Social Factors:** A few respondents highlighted cultural and social barriers that have affected their educational opportunities. These include gender-related restrictions,

societal norms that prioritize certain fields of study over others, and lack of support for non-traditional educational pathways. Discrimination and stereotypes based on cultural background or identity were also mentioned as challenges faced by some respondents.

Despite these challenges, respondents expressed resilience and determination in overcoming barriers to pursue their educational goals. Many highlighted the importance of government support, scholarship programs, and community initiatives in addressing these challenges and promoting educational equity and inclusivity.

Enhanced Learning Experiences

Respondents also emphasized the importance of educational policy in improving learning experiences and encouraging overall development. They included examples of curricular in post COVID-19 reforms, student-centered approaches to teaching and learning, and the incorporation of technology into education, all of which have helped to create a more engaging and successful learning environment. Respondents also emphasized the importance of developing critical thinking, creativity, and soft skills, all of which are necessary for personal growth and success in today's globalized society.

Respondents shared their perspectives on the role of technology in enhancing educational outcomes in Saudi Arabia and identified areas for further leveraging technology in education. Key insights include:

- **Positive Impact of Technology:** Many respondents highlighted the positive impact of technology on educational outcomes, citing benefits such as improved access to learning resources, enhanced communication and collaboration, and personalized learning experiences. They noted the importance of digital platforms, online courses, and educational apps in facilitating remote learning, especially during the COVID-19 pandemic.

- **Digital Skills Development:** Respondents emphasized the importance of integrating technology into the curriculum to develop digital literacy skills among students. They highlighted the need for training programs and resources to support teachers in effectively integrating technology into teaching practices and promoting digital citizenship among students.
- **Enhanced Learning Experiences:** Several respondents underscored the potential of technology to enhance learning experiences through interactive multimedia content, virtual simulations, and gamified learning activities. They emphasized the importance of adopting innovative teaching methods and educational technologies to engage students, promote active learning, and cater to diverse learning styles and preferences.
- **Challenges and Opportunities:** While acknowledging the benefits of technology in education, respondents also identified challenges such as unequal access to technology, digital divide, and concerns related to online safety and privacy. They called for greater investment in digital infrastructure, internet connectivity, and technology training programs to ensure equitable access to educational opportunities for all students.

Furthermore, respondents expressed optimism about the transformative potential of technology in education and emphasized the need for strategic planning and investment to maximize its benefits. They suggested several areas where technology could be further leveraged to enhance educational outcomes, including:

- **Personalized Learning:** Respondents highlighted the importance of leveraging technology to facilitate personalized learning experiences tailored to individual students' needs, interests, and learning styles. They suggested the use of adaptive learning platforms, intelligent tutoring

systems, and data analytics to track student progress and provide targeted support and interventions.

- **Blended Learning:** Many respondents advocated for the integration of technology into traditional teaching methods to create blended learning environments that combine face-to-face instruction with online resources and activities. They emphasized the importance of creating flexible learning pathways that accommodate diverse learning preferences and enable students to learn anytime, anywhere.
- **Digital Assessment and Feedback:** Respondents emphasized the importance of using technology to streamline assessment processes and provide timely feedback to students. They suggested the use of digital assessment tools, online quizzes, and automated grading systems to assess student learning outcomes efficiently and provide constructive feedback that supports student growth and improvement.
- **Collaborative Learning:** Several respondents highlighted the potential of technology to facilitate collaborative learning experiences that promote peer interaction, teamwork, and knowledge sharing. They suggested the use of collaborative tools such as discussion forums, wikis, and virtual classrooms to engage students in collaborative projects, group discussions, and peer review activities.

Respondents recognized the transformative role of technology in education and advocated for its strategic integration to enhance educational outcomes, promote equity and inclusivity, and prepare students for success in the digital age. They underscored the importance of ongoing professional development for educators, investment in digital infrastructure, and collaboration between stakeholders to harness the full potential of technology in advancing education in Saudi Arabia.

Moreover, respondents' thoughts provide vital insights into how Saudi Arabia's education systems affect academic advancement and personal development. These initiatives have had a good impact on people's educational journeys across the country by fostering supportive environments, expanding possibilities, and improving learning experiences. Moving forward, continuous investment in education policies that encourage academic performance and holistic development was critical to guaranteeing Saudi Arabia's students' long-term success and prosperity.

Enhancing Saudi Arabia's Education System: Insights from Respondent Recommendations

As Saudi Arabia moves forward with educational post COVID-19 reform, stakeholder voices play an important role in defining policies and practices that promote diversity, equity, and effectiveness. This article reviews respondents' input and proposals for specific post COVID-19 reforms and improvements to Saudi Arabia's educational system. We focus on responses to Question 14, which asked for thoughts on how to make the educational system more inclusive, equitable, and effective.

1. Constructive Feedback for Improvement

Question 14 asked respondents to propose specific adjustments and improvements aimed at transforming Saudi Arabia's education system into one that meets the different requirements of pupils. Respondents made insightful proposals based on educational equity and social justice theories to address current difficulties and improve educational results (Boyle & Schmierbach, 2019).

2. Enhancing Access to Educational Resources

A recurrent theme in respondents' recommendations was the need to improve access to educational resources such as textbooks, technology, and extracurricular activities. Many

responders underlined the necessity of giving all pupils equal opportunity, regardless of socioeconomic status or geographical location. Suggestions included increasing financing for underserved schools, extending library services, and offering scholarships for further study.

3. Promoting Diversity and Inclusivity

Respondents' comments emphasized the importance of improving access to educational resources such as textbooks, technology, and extracurricular activities. Many respondents emphasized the need of offering all students equal opportunities, regardless of socioeconomic background or geographic location. Suggestions included increasing funding for underserved schools, expanding library services, and providing scholarships for future study.

Implementing Innovative Teaching Methods

Respondents underlined the necessity of increasing access to educational resources like textbooks, technology, and extracurricular activities. Many responders underlined the need of providing equitable opportunity for all kids, regardless of socioeconomic background or geographic location. Suggestions included increasing financing for underserved schools, improving library services, and offering scholarships for further education.

Respondents' views and recommendations provide useful insights into how to improve Saudi Arabia's education system. Policymakers and educators may build a more inclusive, equitable, and successful learning environment for all children by putting access to educational resources first, supporting diversity and inclusivity, and employing new teaching methods. Moving forward, it was critical to listen to stakeholders' voices and work together to create a better future for education in Saudi Arabia.

Result Discussion: Addressing Research Questions on Saudi Arabia's Education Policies

After examining the results and prior discussion above, addressing the study questions and the results collected from the respondents, the following insights can be derived:

1. Evolution of Stipend Allocation

Saudi Arabia's approach to stipend allocation has undergone a remarkable evolution, strategically adapting to the shifting contours of the educational landscape. Initially conceived to support traditional educational pursuits, the allocation of stipends has dynamically expanded to embrace the burgeoning realm of online and distance learning modalities. This adaptive response underscores Saudi Arabia's acute awareness of the imperative to align financial assistance with contemporary educational paradigms. By broadening the scope of stipend eligibility to encompass a diverse array of educational endeavors, including online courses and virtual programs, Saudi Arabia has demonstrated a commitment to inclusivity and accessibility in its educational support initiatives.

2. Impact on Academic Progress and Personal Well-being

The impact of Saudi Arabia's comprehensive education programs transcends mere academic progress, extending profoundly into the realm of personal well-being and overall educational experience. Rooted in Bandura's Social Cognitive Theory, these initiatives engender a palpable surge in motivational impetus among students, catalyzing an earnest pursuit of knowledge and academic excellence. Moreover, the provision of financial assistance cultivates a nurturing and supportive learning environment, wherein students are empowered to navigate academic challenges with confidence and resilience. Such holistic support not only fosters academic success but also nurtures personal growth and development, reaffirming Saudi Arabia's commitment to nurturing a generation of empowered and fulfilled individuals.

In essence, Saudi Arabia's education policies epitomize a transformative force, propelling students towards academic achievement and personal fulfillment within an ever-evolving educational landscape. By aligning stipend allocation with contemporary educational imperatives and fostering a supportive ecosystem conducive to holistic growth, Saudi Arabia emerges as a beacon of educational empowerment, poised to shape the future trajectory of its educational landscape with unwavering resolve and foresight.

CONCLUSION

In summation, the impact of free education and stipend programs in Saudi Arabia is profound and multifaceted, resonating deeply with the aspirations and realities of individuals across the kingdom. Through a comprehensive examination of respondent feedback from key regions including Riyadh, Jeddah, Dammam, and Al Qassim, it becomes apparent that these initiatives serve as catalysts for transformative change in the educational landscape. The provision of free education has emerged as a significant factor in defining educational motivation and aspirations. These programs correlate with Bandura's Social Cognitive Theory, which holds that environmental influences considerably impact individual behaviour. In addition, the pleasant experiences shared with educational stipends highlight the vital significance of financial support in promoting educational pursuits, echoing Adams' Equity Theory, which emphasizes the necessity of fairness and justice in social connections.

The public's assessment of Saudi Arabia's education policies is largely positive, with many respondents recognizing the effectiveness of current programs in increasing access to quality education. However, there is a nuanced appreciation of the importance of continual development, particularly in ensuring equitable access and assistance for students from various socioeconomic backgrounds. This emphasizes the need for continual conversation and collaboration between policymakers and stakeholders in addressing existing gaps and improving policy efficacy. The role of technology in education emerges as a major subject, with respondents acknowledging its ability to transform learning experiences and outcomes. Personalized learning approaches, mixed learning settings, and creative assessment methodologies are examples of technology-enabled learning. These findings highlight the importance of strategic investment in digital infrastructure and teacher training to fully realize technology's potential in promoting education. Moreover, the

transformative impact of ongoing free education and stipend programs in Saudi Arabia is undeniable; by prioritizing access, equity, and innovation, policymakers can build on existing initiatives to create a more inclusive, equitable, and effective education system that enables individuals to reach their full potential and contribute meaningfully to society.

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Appendix I

Permission Letter/Informed Consent Form

Participant's Name: _____

Dear Participant/Parent/Legal Guardian,

Re: Permission to Participate in Research Study

You are invited to participate in a research study titled "Understanding the Impact of Saudi Arabia's Free Education System and Allowance Programs." The study aims to comprehensively examine the effects of Saudi Arabia's educational policies on student access, equity, and learning outcomes. Your voluntary participation is highly valued and important to the success of this research.

Participants will be drawn from schools in key cities such as Jeddah, Riyadh, the Eastern Province, and Al Qassim to ensure a thorough knowledge. Purposive sampling will be used in the study, with factors such as population size, urban or rural setting, socioeconomic status, and educational resources taken into account. The study will use Albert Bandura's Social Cognitive Theory and J. Stacy Adams' Equity Theory to investigate how students' access to education and participation in educational programs affect academic achievement and bridge educational gaps between students from different socioeconomic backgrounds.

Data collection will involve online surveys and virtual interviews to overcome geographical constraints. A mixed methods approach, incorporating quantitative and qualitative data collection and analysis, will provide a thorough understanding of the study's issues.

To participate, please read the following information carefully:

1. Your participation is entirely voluntary, and you have the right to withdraw at any time without penalty or loss of benefits.
2. You will receive a clear explanation of the study, including its objectives, procedures, potential risks and benefits, confidentiality safeguards, and the voluntary nature of participation.
3. You may ask questions and seek clarifications about any aspect of the study before making a decision.
4. Your consent to participate will be obtained through physical or electronic signatures, verbal consent, or written affirmation, based on your preferences and cultural norms.
5. Your privacy and the confidentiality of your information will be strictly maintained. Only the research team will have access to the collected data, and all information will be reported in aggregate form to ensure anonymity.

By signing below, you indicate your informed consent to participate in the research study.

Participant's Signature: _____

Date: _____

Parent/Legal Guardian's Signature (if participant is a minor):

Date: _____

Thank you for considering participation in this research study. If you have any questions or require further information, please contact kurniawanarifmaspul@my.uopeople.edu.

Sincerely,

Kurniawan Arif Maspul
M.Ed Candidate
University of the People

Appendix II

Questionnaire on the Impact of Saudi Arabia's Education Policies

Introduction

Thank you for participating in this significant study. Your input will contribute to a comprehensive understanding of the effects of Saudi Arabia's education policies on access to education, equity, and student learning outcomes. Please take your time to provide thoughtful responses to the following questions. Your confidentiality will be maintained, and your responses will be utilized solely for research purposes.

Section 1: Demographic Information

1. Gender:
 - Male
 - Female
 - Non-binary/Other
2. Age:
 - Under 18
 - 18-25
 - 26-35
 - 36-45
 - Over 45
3. Educational Level
 - Primary School
 - Intermediate School
 - Secondary School
 - Vocational/Technical Education
 - Higher Education (Bachelor's, Master's, or Doctorate)
4. Location
 - Jeddah
 - Riyadh
 - Eastern Province
 - Al Qassim (including Buraydah and Unaizah)
5. Type of School:
 - Public
 - Private
6. Socioeconomic Background:
 - Low Income
 - Middle Income
 - High Income
 - Not Sure/Prefer Not to Answer

Section 2: Impact of Saudi Arabia's Education Policies

7. How has the availability of free education influenced your decision to pursue education?
 - Significantly Increased
 - Increased
 - No Significant Change
 - Decreased
 - Significantly Decreased
8. Have you benefited from any educational stipends or financial assistance programs provided by Saudi Arabia's government? If yes, please describe how it has impacted your educational journey.

[Open-ended response]

9. In your opinion, how effective are the current education policies in Saudi Arabia in promoting access to quality education?
 - Highly Effective
 - Effective
 - Somewhat Effective
 - Ineffective
 - Highly Ineffective
10. Do you believe that the current education policies adequately address the needs of students from diverse socioeconomic backgrounds? Please explain your answer.

[Open-ended response]

Section 3: Academic Progress and Personal Development

11. Reflecting on your academic journey, how have Saudi Arabia's education policies influenced your academic progress and personal development?

[Open-ended response]

12. Have you encountered any barriers or challenges in accessing educational opportunities due to factors such as location, socioeconomic status, or cultural background? If yes, please elaborate.

[Open-ended response]

13. How do you perceive the role of technology in enhancing educational outcomes in Saudi Arabia? Are there any areas where technology could be further leveraged?

[Open-ended response]

Section 4: Feedback and Recommendations

14. What specific changes or improvements would you suggest to make Saudi Arabia's education system more inclusive, equitable, and effective in meeting the needs of students?

[Open-ended response]

15. Is there any other feedback or insights you would like to share regarding your experience with Saudi Arabia's education policies and programs?

[Open-ended response]

Conclusion

Thank you for taking the time to complete this questionnaire. Your valuable insights will contribute to the ongoing efforts to enhance education policies and programs in Saudi Arabia. If you have any additional comments or suggestions, please feel free to contact the research team. Your participation is highly appreciated.

Appendix III

Questionnaire & Interview Tables

Influence of Free Education on Pursuing Education	Number of Respondents
Significantly Increased	15
Increased	20
No Significant Change	10
Decreased	3
Significantly Decreased	2

Impact of Financial Assistance Programs	Impacts
Enabling access to higher education	20
Alleviating financial burden	15
Facilitating pursuit of further studies or specialized programs	5
Empowering individuals from disadvantaged backgrounds	10

Effectiveness of Education Policies	Number of Respondents
Highly Effective	12
Effective	20
Somewhat Effective	10
Ineffective	5
Highly Ineffective	3

Adequacy of Education Policies for Diverse Backgrounds	Suggestions for Improvement
Tailored support for marginalized communities	Providing targeted assistance and resources for students from marginalized backgrounds to address their unique needs and challenges.
More comprehensive financial aid programs	Expanding financial aid programs to provide a broader range of support, including scholarships, grants, and loans, to ensure financial barriers do not hinder students' access to quality education.

Increased accessibility to quality resources and facilities	Ensuring equitable access to high-quality educational resources, including libraries, technology, and infrastructure, across all schools and regions to create a level playing field for all students.
Enhanced teacher training and curriculum diversity	Investing in professional development programs for teachers to enhance their skills in addressing the needs of students from diverse backgrounds and promoting inclusive teaching practices. Additionally, promoting diversity in curricula by incorporating diverse perspectives, cultures, and histories to provide a more inclusive and representative educational experience.